

**Mapping the Universe:
Improving Photometric Redshift Accuracy and Computational
Efficiency**

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Mapping the Universe: Improving Photometric Redshift Accuracy and Computational Efficiency

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Abstract

Correctly modeling and fitting the spectral energy distributions (SED) of galaxies is a crucial component of extracting accurate and reliable photometric redshifts (photo-z’s) from large-scale extragalactic photometric surveys. However, most codes today are unable to derive photo-z’s to the required precision needed for future surveys such as *Euclid* in feasible amounts of time. To better understand the general features an improved photo-z search should possess, we characterize the shape of the photo-z likelihood surface for several objects with a pre-generated grid of ~ 2 million elements, finding that most surfaces are significantly “bumpy” with gradients dominated by large degeneracies outside the region(s) of peak probability. Based on these results, we design an algorithm to efficiently explore pre-computed grids that combines a swarm intelligence version of a Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC)-driven approach with simulated annealing. Using a mock catalog of $\sim 380,000$ COSMOS galaxies, we show that our new algorithm is at least 40–50 times more efficient compared to standard grid-based counterparts while retaining equivalent accuracy. Following this, we develop a new perturbative approach to generating SEDs from a set of “baseline” photometry that can rapidly generate photometry from continuous changes in redshift, reddening, and emission line strengths to sub-percent level accuracy. By combining this approach with an appropriate set of priors, we establish a framework for using what we term “fuzzy” templates, which allows for the use of expanded template libraries in photo-z searches that can simultaneously account for intrinsic, empirical variation in both reddening and individual emission line strengths for a given galaxy template. Finally, we briefly explore the use of importance nested sampling (INS) to better capture multimodal redshift probability distributions. Our findings lay the groundwork for significant improvements in future photo-z searches.

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Table of Contents

1	Introduction	6
2	From Observed SED to Photometric Redshift	9
2.1	Constructing an Effective GOF Metric	9
2.2	Creating Model Photometry	15
2.3	SED Fitting	22
2.3.1	Fixed (Grid-based) Template Fitting	22
2.3.2	Adaptive (MCMC) Template Fitting	24
2.4	Deriving PDFs from the SED Fitting Process	26
3	Improving Pre-Existing Fitting Methodologies with BAD-Z	28
3.1	Generating a Realistic Mock Catalog	29
3.2	Characterizing the Parameter Space	33
3.2.1	Exploring Structure in 2D Redshift-Reddening Subspace	33
3.2.2	The Full Redshift-Galaxy-Dust-Reddening Search	36
3.3	Creating an Effective Photo-z Algorithm	38
3.4	Comparison with Grid-Based Code	44
4	Developing a New Photo-z Framework	48
4.1	Beyond the Grid: Perturbative Model Generation	48
4.1.1	Generating “Baseline” Photometry	49
4.1.2	Incorporating Reddening Effects	52
4.2	Sampling Color Space Directly with “Fuzzy Templates”	58
4.3	Capturing Widely Separated Degeneracies using Importance Nested Sampling	65
4.3.1	Nested Sampling	65
4.3.2	Ellipsoidal Decomposition in MULTINEST	68
4.3.3	Importance Nested Sampling	69

5 Conclusion **72**

A An Expanded Parameterization of Extragalactic Dust Curves **75**

1. Introduction

Over the last two decades, a combination of deep and wide-field multi-wavelength surveys have allowed us to study large samples of galaxies over a wide redshift (z) range in unprecedented detail. Advances in stellar population synthesis (SPS) modelling (Bruzual & Charlot 2003; Maraston 2005; Conroy 2013) and improved global diagnostics of galactic star formation (e.g., Kennicutt & Evans 2012) have also enabled the determination of key physical quantities based on these data from stellar masses (M_*) and star formation rates (SFRs; ψ) to dust attenuation ($A(\lambda)$) and even star formation histories (SFHs; $\psi(t)$).

In order to derive the majority of these quantities, the redshift of an object must be known. Spectroscopic redshifts (spec- z 's; z_s) often provide extremely precise measurements at the cost of being observationally time-consuming. In order to derive redshifts for much larger photometric datasets in feasible amounts of time, extragalactic astronomers often resort to fitting spectral energy distributions (SEDs) taken from a combination of broad- and/or narrow-band photometry.

Using these “photometric redshifts” (photo- z 's; z_p), astronomers have been able to determine accurate rest-frame colors for many extragalactic objects. These suggest galaxies out to high redshift seem to fall into two distinct groups in color space, often classified as “star-forming” and “quiescent” (Williams et al. 2009; Ilbert et al. 2013; Arnouts et al. 2013). Studies of derived stellar masses and dust-corrected SFRs have revealed key differences between these groups (Salim et al. 2007; Schiminovich et al. 2007; Williams et al. 2009; Brammer et al. 2011; Ilbert et al. 2013; Behroozi et al. 2013) suggesting that evolving relationships both within them (e.g., the tight $M_* - \psi$ correlation among star-forming galaxies; Brinchmann et al. 2004; Noeske et al. 2007; Speagle et al. 2014) and between them (e.g., the transfer of mass between the two groups over cosmic time; Bell et al. 2007) are intimately linked to the rapid “quenching” of star formation (Schawinski et al. 2014) and the “downsizing paradigm” (that more massive objects seem to evolve more quickly; Lilly et al. 1996; Madau et al. 1996; Hopkins & Beacom 2006). In addition, they have also provided fundamental insights into the extent that internal gas dynamics, star formation, and galaxy environment can influence galaxy evolution (Peng et al. 2010, 2012; Steinhardt & Speagle 2014; Kelson 2014; Abramson et al. 2014b,a; Lin et al. 2014).

Furthermore, photo- z 's are particularly important for future surveys trying to constrain dark energy via, e.g., weak gravitational lensing (Albrecht et al. 2006; Bordoloi et al. 2010, 2012), galaxy clustering (Eisenstein et al. 2005; Levi et al. 2013), and type Ia supernovae (Riess et al. 1998). Due to the enormous sample sizes planned for projects such as the joint ESA-NASA space-based *Euclid* mission (expected launch date 2020) and the Large Synoptic Survey Telescope (LSST; expected first light in 2021), photo- z 's are the only effective way to measure redshifts to these billions of objects in a reasonable amount of time. To effectively utilize these huge future data sets, photo- z 's with a very low level of residual systematics (on the order of $< 0.5\%$) are needed (Huterer et al. 2006; Bordoloi et al. 2010, 2012). Developing an efficient and accurate photo- z code is thus of major importance to conducting science in the era of “big data” extragalactic astronomy.

While photo- z 's in general are quite accurate, exhibiting $\sim 0.8\text{--}3\%$ 1σ scatter relative to their spec- z counterparts (Ilbert et al. 2013), they can be subject to “catastrophic errors” where the derived photo- z 's and their spec- z counterparts disagree by more than a (large) given quality threshold η_{cat} ($\eta \equiv \frac{|z_p - z_s|}{1 + z_s}$), where most often $\eta_{\text{cat}} = 0.15$.¹ Aside from misfits caused by bad photometry, a small number of bands, and/or a multimodal redshift probability distribution function (PDF), such catastrophic failures often occur when prominent spectral features (e.g., the Lyman and Balmer breaks at 1260 and 4000 Å) that normally help to constrain the redshift are confused (Sobral et al. 2013; Steinhardt et al. 2014). The frequency of these catastrophic errors can range from a few percent to around half of the spec- z comparison sample (Sobral et al. 2012; Dahlen et al. 2013; Steinhardt et al. 2014), and their impacts on the derived physical properties used in studies have yet to be fully explored (although see Speagle et al. 2014). Areas where photo- z codes have been rigorously tested, however, indicate that existing codes also exhibit biases, with photo- z 's underpredicting their spec- z counterparts by $\sim 1\text{--}2\%$ (Hildebrandt et al. 2010; Dahlen et al. 2013).

In addition to catastrophic errors and systematic biases, photo- z codes today also suffer from several modelling and computational deficiencies. Due to an insufficient understanding of the relevant parameter space, many codes today rely on pre-generated “grids” of model galaxy photometry to try and probe the regions of interest (although see Ménard et al. 2013 for a different approach). This crude, brute-force approach not only results in maximally inefficient sampling but also requires trade-offs in parameter resolution in order to remain computationally viable. As a result, current codes are too slow and inaccurate to determine photo- z 's to the required quality needed for these future dark energy surveys.² These problems are frequently exacerbated by the limited physical range probed by existing libraries of empirical galaxy templates (Ilbert et al. 2013; Brown et al. 2014), emission line scaling relations (Ilbert et al. 2009; Cowie et al. 2011; Stark et al. 2013; Salmon et al. 2014), and dust attenuation curves (Bolzonella et al. 2000; Ilbert et al. 2009; Speagle et al. 2014) used to construct these grids, as well as the overly simplistic assumption of a uniform dust screen used to generate reddened photometry (Conroy 2013).

Due to their common (and necessary) use in extragalactic studies, current photo- z (in)accuracy levels, catastrophic error rates, intrinsic biases, modelling (over)dependencies, and template deficiencies are concerning. However, even more concerning is the computational inefficiency of most modern photo- z codes – tied to their current reliance on grids – given how many future surveys will depend on them.

¹For most applications (e.g., Dahlen et al. 2013), the reported photo- z /spec- z scatter is calculated after removing all catastrophic errors and assuming the distribution is approximately Gaussian.

²Note that this issue is not confined to grid-based approaches. Monte Carlo Markov Chain (MCMC)-based approaches are inefficient, albeit for different reasons (see §3), and although machine learning methods tend to be efficient once the initial set of mappings have been constructed, determining uncertainties (i.e. the full $P(z)$ distribution) frequently requires the application of Monte Carlo-based techniques (see, e.g., Carrasco Kind & Brunner 2014b), leading to similar computational inefficiencies.

This thesis attempts to rectify several of these issues in order to develop a faster, more flexible photo-z code:

- In § 2, we give a statistical overview of how template fitting codes work. This includes an outline of the methodology behind deriving an effective goodness-of-fit (GOF) metric, an overview of how traditional template fitting codes generate model photometry and probe the relevant regions of parameter space, and how to use this information to determine the associated redshift PDF (i.e. deriving uncertainties).
- In § 3, we investigate possible methods that traditional template fitting codes might use to more efficiently search a pre-generated grid. We explore the overall shape of both a reduced subset of and the full parameter space for individual objects, and use these “maps” to inform our eventual algorithm. Our findings lead us to develop **BAD-Z (Brisk Annealing Driven Redshifts (Z))**, a Monte Carlo Markov Chain (MCMC)-like approach based on `emcee` Foreman-Mackey et al. (2013) and supplemented by a simulated annealing metaheuristic. We compare the results to a grid-based counterpart **GRIPEZ (GRID-based Photometric Estimation of Redshifts (Z))** using a set of mock photometry generated from $\sim 380,000$ galaxies in the COSMOS (Scoville et al. 2007) field.
- In § 4, we investigate ways to improve on the limitations inherent in **BAD-Z**, including methods to generate photometry not confined to a pre-generated grid and more sophisticated sampling techniques that can better recover multi-modal distributions. By constructing a series of interpolations and approximations over a number of photometric grids, we develop a new “perturbative” approach to generate photometry for a continuous range of parameters at (sub-)percent level accuracy. Using this new approach, we develop a framework for incorporating an expanded set of “fuzzy” templates – templates that empirically incorporate intrinsic variation in reddening and emission line strengths – that can better explore the full range of color space spanned by observable galaxies at a wide range of redshifts. We also briefly investigate importance nested sampling (INS) techniques via `MULTINEST` (Feroz & Hobson 2008; Feroz et al. 2009, 2013) as a means to probe common but widely-separated degeneracies in parameter space that MCMC-based approaches fail to capture.
- In § 5, we summarize and discuss several of the main features of our results, including possible future extensions of this work.

Throughout this work, we standardize to the AB magnitude system (Oke & Gunn 1983) and an $(h, \Omega_m, \Omega_\Lambda) = (0.7, 0.3, 0.7)$ concordance cosmology.

2. From Observed SED to Photometric Redshift

There are four main functions an effective photo-z fitting routine must be able to perform:

1. Determine an effective GOF metric that can take into account statistical and systematic uncertainties when comparing model photometry (\vec{F}_{model}) to the observed data (\vec{F}_{obs}).
2. Generate model photometry from a list of model parameters (\vec{x}).
3. Sample effectively from the range spanned by the model parameters (i.e. the available parameter space) to determine the best fit.
4. Derive the marginalized redshift PDF $P(z)$ from the fitting process.

We will discuss each of these in turn, focusing on how they are implemented in most photo-z codes in use today.

2.1. Constructing an Effective GOF Metric

In order to derive accurate photo-z's, we must first determine what GOF metric we wish to use to determine the quality of our fits. While there are many possible choices, most routines opt to use the simple χ^2 GOF metric in order to incorporate uncertainties on the photometry and/or model in a straightforward manner. However, χ^2 does not incorporate upper limits, leading many codes to (incorrectly) implement ad-hoc procedures to include them (Sawicki 2012). In order to rectify this error, the general process of deriving an effective GOF metric from a set of underlying probability distributions associated with a set of individual observations is outlined below.

For a given set of observed photometry \vec{F}_{obs} , the probability P_i that a component of the relevant set of observed data $F_{\text{obs},i}$ has been produced from the analogous component of a given model $F_{\text{model},i}$ is

$$P_i \propto \exp \left[-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{F_{\text{obs},i} - sF_{\text{model},i}}{\sigma_i} \right)^2 \right] dF_{\text{obs},i}, \quad (1)$$

where s is an arbitrary scaling factor and the errors are normally distributed and independent of both the flux and each other such that the total variance $\sigma_i^2 = \sigma_{\text{obs},i}^2 + \sigma_{\text{model},i}^2$.³ An illustration of this process is shown in Figure 1.

³This assumption only holds when objects are either observed at high signal-to-noise or are detector/background-limited (i.e. are fainter than the sky). For observations detected above the background but at modest S/N, the variances instead scale with the photon flux.

Fig. 1.— A schematic illustration of how an observed flux F_{obs} (black distribution) is fit relative to a scaled model flux sF_{model} (blue dashed line) assuming normally distributed errors. The minimum $\chi^2(s)$ is achieved by minimizing the normalized distances between the collection of $\{F_{\text{obs}}\}$ and $\{sF_{\text{model}}\}$ values.

The probability that the entire set of data points in a given observation \vec{F}_{obs} is consistent with a corresponding set of model data \vec{F}_{model} is then

$$P \propto \prod_i P_i \propto \exp \left[-\frac{1}{2} \sum_i \left(\frac{F_{\text{obs},i} - sF_{\text{model},i}}{\sigma_i} \right)^2 \right] = \exp \left[-\frac{1}{2} \chi^2 \right], \quad (2)$$

where

$$\chi^2 \equiv -2 \ln P = \sum_i \left(\frac{F_{\text{obs},i} - sF_{\text{model},i}}{\sigma_i} \right)^2. \quad (3)$$

As a result, for normally distributed errors the standard χ^2 -statistic ends up being a natural GOF metric.

To maximize P , we then simply need to minimize $\chi^2(\vec{x}, s)$. As s is a simple scaling factor (i.e. $\chi^2(s)$ is quadratic), for a given \vec{x} we can marginalize over s by solving

$$\frac{\partial \chi^2}{\partial s} = 0, \quad (4)$$

which gives us:

$$s = \frac{\sum_i \frac{F_{\text{obs},i} F_{\text{model},i}}{\sigma_i^2}}{\sum_i \frac{F_{\text{model},i}^2}{\sigma_i^2}}. \quad (5)$$

Solving for s in the standard χ^2 formulation above is thus a simple one-step process and can be calculated prior to computing an actual χ^2 value.

For many astronomical observations, however, often only a subset $\vec{F}_{\text{obs},I}$ of the components in \vec{F}_{obs} are actually made available – the remaining $\vec{F}_{\text{obs},J}$ components are instead treated as upper limits that provide limited (but important) information.⁴ While such practices are understandable when working in a logarithmic basis where low signal-to-noise (S/N) data are hard to represent (Lupton et al. 1999), reducing a best-estimate flux and associated error to an upper limit not only removes useful information, but also makes the mathematical implementation significantly more complicated.

For upper limits, the corresponding probability that a portion of an observation $F_{\text{obs},j}$ comes from the corresponding model $F_{\text{model},j}$ can be derived by integrating over the normal distribution up to the corresponding upper limit $F_{\text{lim},j} = N\sigma_j$ for a given s ,

$$P_j \propto \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} \frac{1}{\sigma_j} \int_{-\infty}^{F_{\text{lim},j}} \exp \left[-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{F_j - sF_{\text{model},j}}{\sigma_j} \right)^2 \right] dF_j. \quad (6)$$

In other words, we attempt to find the best scaling factor for a given model that maximizes the probability contained under the subsequent distribution below the upper limit. An illustration of this process is shown in Figure 2.

We can then derive the total probability that a given observation containing both detections ($\vec{F}_{\text{obs},I}$) and upper limits ($\vec{F}_{\text{obs},J}$) is consistent with a corresponding set of model photometry \vec{F}_{model} by multiplying both of these components together so that

$$\begin{aligned} P \propto \prod_i P_i \prod_j P_j &\propto \exp \left[-\frac{1}{2} \sum_i \left(\frac{F_{\text{obs},i} - sF_{\text{model},i}}{\sigma_i} \right)^2 \right] \\ &\times \prod_j \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} \frac{1}{\sigma_j} \int_{-\infty}^{F_{\text{lim},j}} \exp \left[-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{F_j - sF_{\text{model},j}}{\sigma_j} \right)^2 \right] dF_j. \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Based on this, we can now define a new χ^2 metric,

$$\chi_{\text{mod}}^2 \equiv -2 \ln(P_I P_J) \equiv \chi_I^2 + \chi_{\text{up},J}^2, \quad (8)$$

⁴In this section, capital versions of subscripts are used for convenience to refer to the subset of data constructed from all components indexed by the corresponding lower-case subscript. For instance, $\vec{F}_{\text{obs},I}$ refers to the set of components that would be included in the sum $\sum_i F_{\text{obs},i}$.

Fig. 2.— A schematic illustration of how an observed flux upper limit F_{lim} is fit relative to a scaled model flux sF_{model} assuming normally distributed errors. The minimum $\chi_{\text{up}}^2(s)$ is achieved by maximizing the probability contained under the distribution (shaded blue) for the collection of $\{F_{\text{lim}}\}$ and $s\{F_{\text{model}}\}$ values.

where we have defined

$$\chi_I^2 = \sum_i \left(\frac{F_{\text{obs},i} - sF_{\text{model},i}}{\sigma_i} \right)^2 \quad (9)$$

as the usual χ^2 statistic and

$$\chi_{\text{up},J}^2 = -2 \sum_j \ln \left\{ \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} \frac{1}{\sigma_j} \int_{-\infty}^{F_{\text{lim},j}} \exp \left[-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{F - sF_{\text{model},j}}{\sigma_j} \right)^2 \right] dF \right\} \quad (10)$$

as a modifying term that incorporates the information content coming from upper limits.

Unlike the standard χ^2 metric, $\chi_{\text{mod}}^2(s)$ is not strictly quadratic in s . As a result, we are unable to analytically marginalize over s to determine the minimum χ_{mod}^2 value and must instead resort to numerical methods.

These can be implemented in one of two ways. First, we can attempt to minimize the above function, which can be recast into a more tractable form using the complementary error function,

$$\text{erfc}(x) \equiv 1 - \text{erf}(x) = 1 - \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \int_0^x e^{-t^2} dt = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \int_x^\infty e^{-t^2} dt.$$

Fig. 3.— Normalized flux for a sample catalog object (black circles) with the best-fitting model photometry ($z = 1.995$, unextincted star-forming spiral template) overlaid (green squares). The data are well-fit by the model (reduced- $\chi^2 = 1.23$).

Letting $t = \frac{F - sF_{\text{model},j}}{\sqrt{2}\sigma_j}$, $dt = \frac{dF}{\sqrt{2}\sigma_j}$, and $x = -F_{\text{lim},j}$, we get

$$\chi_{\text{up},J}^2 = -2 \sum_j \ln \left[\text{erfc} \left(\frac{F_{\text{lim},j} - sF_{\text{model},j}}{\sqrt{2}\sigma_j} \right) \right]. \quad (11)$$

Alternately, we can solve for the roots of $\frac{\partial \chi_{\text{mod}}^2}{\partial s} = \frac{\partial \chi_{\text{up},J}^2}{\partial s} + \frac{\partial \chi_{\text{up},J}^2}{\partial s} = 0$, which gives

$$\sum_i \frac{F_{\text{obs},i} F_{\text{model},i} - s F_{\text{model},i}^2}{\sigma_i^2} - \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} \sum_j \frac{F_{\text{model},j} \exp \left[-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{F_{\text{lim},j} - sF_{\text{model},j}}{\sigma_j} \right)^2 \right]}{\sigma_j \text{erfc} \left(\frac{F_{\text{lim},j} - sF_{\text{model},j}}{\sqrt{2}\sigma_j} \right)} = 0. \quad (12)$$

While both the latter expressions are significantly more computationally intensive to solve than the original, both give unambiguous best-fit GOF values for a given set of \vec{F}_{obs} , $\vec{\sigma}_{\text{obs}}$, \vec{F}_{model} , and $\vec{\sigma}_{\text{model}}$ vectors.⁵

⁵We again note that the standard χ^2 metric can be used with any type of data, regardless of how low any individual observation's S/N value might be. As a result, it is often more useful to undertake SED fitting in linear *flux* space (which can accommodate negative fluxes present in low-S/N data) rather than in logarithmic *magnitude* space (which cannot).

Fig. 4.— Noisier photometry of the object in Figure 3. To generate the new fluxes, we boosted the errors on the original fluxes by a factor of 3, resampled the photometry, and then assigned 5σ upper limits.

We illustrate the effects that upper limits can have on $\chi_{\text{mod}}^2(s)$ using a sample object taken from a mock catalog (see §3.1). The photometry of the object along with the best-fitting model is shown in Figure 3. To introduce several upper limits, we boost the errors on the object by a factor of 3, resample the photometry, and reassign 5σ upper limits. The new, noisier photometry is shown in Figure 4.

Using the same model photometry, we compute $\chi_{\text{mod}}^2(s)$ assuming the calculated upper limits were actually at 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5σ (the last being the true value). Each of these new upper limits contains different information content – possibly disfavoring the original model we are fitting – and affects the general shape of the $\chi_{\text{mod}}^2(s)$ function. By exploring a range of possible upper limits then, we are able to examine how $\chi_{\text{mod}}^2(s)$ behaves in several different regimes. These functions are shown relative to the base case (i.e. no upper limits) in Figure 5, where the asymmetric nature of the upper limits is clearly visible in each of the modified cases. In addition, the change in best-fit scale factor and $\chi_{\text{mod,min}}^2$ due to the assumed scale of the upper limit can also be seen, illustrating the changing information content the different upper limit thresholds provide in each case.

Fig. 5.— χ_{mod}^2 as a function of the scaling factor s for the modified photometry from Figure 4 assuming the same model shown in Figure 3. The functions are plotted assuming the calculated upper limit thresholds are actually indicative $N = 1-5\sigma$ upper limits (5σ being the true value). For clarity, the true functions (solid) have also been shifted down (dashed) and the minima (thin dashed lines, filled circles) indicated. Each of these new upper limits contains different information content – possibly disfavoring the original model we are investigating – and allowing us to observe how the $\chi_{\text{mod}}^2(s)$ function behaves more generally. The asymmetric nature caused by the inclusion of the upper limits in each function can be clearly seen relative to the original χ^2 function (black). The change in best-fit scale factor and $\chi_{\text{mod},\text{min}}^2$ due to the assumed scale of the upper limit is also visible. The value of correctly incorporating upper limits (as opposed to imposing arbitrary probability distributions) can be clearly seen in the “correct” case (5σ), where we derive a scaling factor $< 0.5\%$ off from the true value.

2.2. Creating Model Photometry

In order for template fitting codes to function effectively, they must be able to construct a forward map \mathcal{P} from a set of parameters \vec{x} to a set of model photometry. This can be compared to the data to give a relevant GOF value for a specific set of trial parameters \vec{x}_i , which is then used to determine the location of the next trial parameters \vec{x}_{i+1} .

To generate effective model photometry \vec{F}_{model} , most codes begin with a set of “base” galaxy templates $S_{\lambda,\text{base}}$ (here listed in units of flux density per unit wavelength). These base templates are then used to construct “starting” galaxy templates via some parameters \vec{a} . This is most often

Fig. 6.— The 31 base galaxy templates (in units of F_λ and normalized at $1.6 \mu\text{m}$) used to compute photo-z’s for the COSMOS survey. These span a wide range of activity from passive ellipticals (red) to extremely active starbursts (blue). The templates are constructed using a mixture of empirical spectra from Polletta et al. (2007) and SPS models from Bruzual & Charlot (2003) assuming exponentially declining SFHs. These are representative of most of the base template sets used by photo-z codes today.

done by linear combination,

$$S_{\lambda,\text{start}}(\lambda|\vec{a}) = \sum_i a_i S_{\lambda,\text{base},i}(\lambda), \quad (13)$$

where the a_i ’s are usually non-negative and i spans the range of available base galaxy templates (see Figure 6). In some cases, \vec{a} is a simple selection vector (i.e. $a_i = 1$ for some particular i and $a_{j \neq i} = 0$ everywhere else) so $S_{\lambda,\text{start}}(\lambda|i) = S_{\lambda,\text{base},i}(\lambda)$.

These templates are often modified with a set of emission lines that can be treated as a collection of separate emission line templates $S_{\lambda,\text{em}}$, such as the template shown in Figure 7. These are added to the previous “starting” template to create new underlying galaxy templates

$$S_{\lambda,\text{gal}}(\lambda|\vec{a}, \vec{b}) = S_{\lambda,\text{start}}(\lambda|\vec{a}) + \sum_j b_j S_{\lambda,\text{em},j}(\lambda), \quad (14)$$

where $b_j \geq 0$ and j spans the range of base emission line templates. These are usually normalized

Fig. 7.— An updated version of the emission line template/prescription (in units of F_λ) used to compute photo- z 's for the COSMOS survey. Fluxes are calibrated based on the scaling relations contained in Kennicutt (1998), Ilbert et al. (2009), Hao et al. (2011), and Murphy et al. (2011) and normalized relative to the FUV flux in the *GALEX* FUV filter assuming a FWHM of 200 km/s.

to the total integrated line flux F_{line} or the corresponding equivalent width (EW),

$$\text{EW}_\lambda(\text{line}) = \int \frac{F_{\text{obs}} - F_{\text{cont}}}{F_{\text{cont}}} d\lambda, \quad (15)$$

where F_{obs} is the observed flux across the emission line around wavelength λ , F_{cont} is the (estimated) continuum level underneath the emission line, and EW_λ is usually measured in \AA .⁶

“Effective” galaxy templates $S_{\lambda,\text{eff}}$ are then created by superimposing a uniform galactic dust screen such that

$$S_{\lambda,\text{eff}}(\lambda|\vec{a}, \vec{b}, \vec{c}, s_r) = S_{\lambda,\text{gal}}(\lambda|\vec{a}, \vec{b}) \times \mathcal{R}_{\text{gal}}(\lambda|\vec{c}, s_r), \quad (16)$$

where

$$\mathcal{R}_{\text{gal}}(\lambda|\vec{c}, s_r) = 10^{-0.4(s_r \times \sum_l c_l A_{\text{gal,base},l}(\lambda))} \quad (17)$$

⁶In many cases \vec{b} is not a free parameter, but rather fixed to a set of constant values (Ilbert et al. 2009) or a function of some subset of the total parameters included in the fit (Salmon et al. 2014).

Fig. 8.— An updated version of the reddening laws (normalized to $k(\lambda \geq 2.5 \mu\text{m}) = 0$) used to compute photo- z 's for the COSMOS survey. These include two from the Milky Way (Allen 1976; Seaton 1979), one from the Large Magellanic Cloud (Fitzpatrick 1986), one from the Small Magellanic Cloud (Prevot et al. 1984), and one derived from a collection of starburst galaxies (Calzetti et al. 2000). As not all individual data points (circles) are listed in the relevant papers, some are plotted for illustrative purposes. The extension of limited data to longer wavelengths as well as the derivation of our parameterized fits (solid lines) are discussed in Appendix A.

is a function of the set of wavelength-dependent dust attenuation curves $\{A_{\text{gal,base},l}(\lambda)\}$ and a corresponding scale factor s_r . Most often, $A(\lambda)$ is measured in magnitudes and normalized to the extinction in the B and V bands,

$$E(B-V) \equiv A(B) - A(V) \quad (18)$$

so that

$$k(\lambda) \equiv A(\lambda)/E(B-V). \quad (19)$$

Defining

$$k_{\text{gal}}(\lambda|\vec{c}) = \sum_l c_l k_{\text{gal,base},l}(\lambda), \quad (20)$$

$$R_{\text{gal}}(\lambda|\vec{c}) = 10^{-0.4 \times k_{\text{gal}}(\lambda|\vec{c})}, \quad (21)$$

where $c_l \geq 0$ and l spans the range of available dust curves, we can then write a more explicit formulation of \mathcal{R}_{gal} ,

$$\mathcal{R}_{\text{gal}}(\lambda|\vec{c}, E(B-V)) = 10^{-0.4 \times E(B-V) \times k_{\text{gal}}(\lambda|\vec{c})} = [\mathcal{R}_{\text{gal}}(\lambda|\vec{c})]^{E(B-V)}. \quad (22)$$

As is the case with the galaxy templates, often \vec{c} is just a selection vector. Note that the construction of these dust curves over the same wavelength ranges probed by a set of corresponding galaxy templates is often a non-trivial task, as discussed in Appendix A. A representative set of such a set of dust curves is shown in Figure 8.

These effective galaxy templates are then redshifted by $(1+z)$ and modified by extinction from intervening clouds of neutral hydrogen (H-clouds) in the intergalactic medium (IGM) using the formalism presented in Madau (1995) in order to form the final “model” galaxy template $S_{\lambda, \text{model}}$. In brief,

$$S_{\lambda, \text{model}}(\lambda|\vec{a}, \vec{b}, \vec{c}, E(B-V), z) = S_{\lambda, \text{eff}}(\lambda|\vec{a}, \vec{b}, \vec{c}, E(B-V)) \times \mathcal{R}_{\text{IGM}}(\lambda|z), \quad (23)$$

$$\mathcal{R}_{\text{IGM}}(\lambda|z) = \exp[\tau_1(\lambda|z) + \tau_2(\lambda|z)], \quad (24)$$

where, defining $\lambda_z \equiv \lambda(1+z)$,

$$\tau_1(\lambda_z) = \sum_i f_i \left(\frac{\lambda_z}{\lambda_{0,i}} \right)^{3.46} \quad \text{if } \lambda_z < \lambda_{0,z,i}, \quad (25)$$

where i increments through the (redshifted) emission lines $\lambda_{0,z,i}$ present in the Lyman series⁷, and

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_2(\lambda_z) &= 0.25x_c^3 (x_e^{0.46} - x_c^{0.46}) + 9.4x_c^{1.5} (x_e^{0.18} - x_c^{0.18}) \\ &- 0.7x_c^3 (x_e^{-1.32} - x_c^{-1.32}) - 0.023 (x_e^{1.68} - x_c^{1.68}) \\ &\text{if } S_{\lambda, \text{eff}}(\lambda_z) < \lambda_{z, \text{ion}}, \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

where $x_c = \frac{\lambda_z}{\lambda_{\text{ion}}}$, $x_e = (1+z)$, and $\lambda_{\text{ion}} = 912.0 \text{ \AA}$.⁸ A set of $\mathcal{R}_{\text{IGM}}(\lambda|z)$ curves at several different redshifts in the galaxy rest-frame are shown in Figure 9.

After determining $S_{\lambda, \text{model}}(\lambda)$, the final set of model photometry can be generated by convolving the model galaxy flux density (converted to S_ν) with the transmission $T_i(\nu)$ of a particular filter normalized to a source at constant flux density over the corresponding redshifted wavelengths λ_z ,

$$F_{\text{model},i}^z \propto \mathcal{F}_i(S_{\nu, \text{model}}(\nu)) \equiv \frac{\int_{\lambda_z} S_{\nu, \text{model}}(\nu) T_i(\nu) \nu^{-1} d\nu}{\int_{\lambda_z} T_i(\nu) \nu^{-1} d\nu}, \quad (27)$$

⁷For the first 11 lines, the relevant coefficients are $\vec{\lambda}_0 = \{1216.0, 1026.0, 973.0, 950.0, 938.1, 931.0, 926.5, 923.4, 921.2, 919.6, 918.4\} \text{ \AA}$ and $\vec{f} = \{0.0037, 0.00177, 0.00106, 0.000584, 0.00044, 0.00040, 0.00037, 0.00035, 0.00033, 0.00032, 0.00031\}$.

⁸In any cases where the approximation leads to $\tau_2 < 0$, τ_2 is instead set to 0.

Fig. 9.— A series of $\mathcal{R}_{\text{IGM}}(\lambda)$ curves computed over a range of redshifts and plotted in the rest frame according to the prescription from (Madau 1995). The portion of the curve that would affect the FUV–NUV flux (1000–3000 Å) of a template in the observed frame is highlighted in red. The abrupt, step-like changes in reddening seen between 912 Å and 1216 Å are due to absorption lines from the Lyman series in the galaxy rest-frame, while the smooth bump below 912 Å (the “Lyman limit”) is due to absorption over a variety of redshifts.

where $\mathcal{F}_i^z(S_\nu)$ (measured in units of flux density assuming an AB normalization) is the i th component of the filter convolution function at a particular redshift \mathcal{F}^z .

This process allows us to construct a model template function \mathcal{M} that maps a set of initial templates/functions – $\{S_{\lambda,\text{base}}\}$, $\{S_{\lambda,\text{em}}\}$, $\{\mathcal{R}_{\text{gal}}\}$, and \mathcal{R}_{IGM} – and corresponding set of parameters $\vec{x} = \{\vec{a}; \vec{b}; \vec{c}; E(B-V); z\}$ to a corresponding model template,

$$\mathcal{M}(\vec{x} | \{S_{\lambda,\text{base}}\}, \{S_{\lambda,\text{em}}\}, \{\mathcal{R}_{\text{gal}}\}, \mathcal{R}_{\text{IGM}}) = S_{\nu,\text{model}}(\lambda). \quad (28)$$

The final model photometry can then be derived via

$$\{S_{\lambda,\text{base}}\}, \{S_{\lambda,\text{em}}\}, \{\mathcal{R}_{\text{gal}}\}, \mathcal{R}_{\text{IGM}} \xrightarrow{\mathcal{M}(\vec{x})} S_{\nu,\text{model}}(\lambda) \xrightarrow{\mathcal{F}^z(S_\nu)} \vec{F}_{\text{model}}. \quad (29)$$

This allows us to write the associated “traditional” photometry generating function $\mathcal{P}_{\text{trad}}$ as

$$\mathcal{P}_{\text{trad}}(\vec{x} | \mathcal{F}^z, \mathcal{M}) \equiv \mathcal{F}^z(\mathcal{M}(\vec{x})) = \vec{F}_{\text{model}}, \quad (30)$$

where \mathcal{M} can be seen as executing a number of modifications to a pre-existing set of templates

Fig. 10.— A schematic of how model photometry is traditionally generated for a given set of parameters and a collection of galaxy, emission line, and reddening templates. The starting galaxy template (black) is first modified by adding on emission lines (purple) before being reddened by a uniform galactic dust screen (red). The template is then redshifted (orange) and reddened by the IGM (green) before being convolved with a given filter set (blue; see also Figure 12) to compute the final model photometry (blue circles).

based on a given set of inputs \vec{x} , and \mathcal{F}^z is simply the convolution as a function of redshift of the associated final model template $S_{\nu,\text{model}}$ with a given set of filters.⁹

An illustration of this forward-mapping process is shown in Figure 10. As can be seen there, the $\mathcal{P}_{\text{trad}}$ function is computationally expensive and involves several addition, multiplication, and power operations on several large arrays.

In addition, most implementations of $\mathcal{P}_{\text{trad}}$ do not (re)sample the templates and filters to be on the same $\log(1+z)$ scale (given a predefined grid of redshifts). As a result, for every redshift

⁹Errors on the final model photometry can be derived using the same process outlined in this section, except with $S_{\nu,\text{model}}(\lambda)$ replaced everywhere by the wavelength-dependent error on the model galaxy template $\sigma_{\text{model}}(\lambda)$. Alternately, σ_{model} can be set ad-hoc on the final combined template and/or the output photometry to account for, e.g., uncertainties in emission line contamination.

value probed the corresponding templates and/or filters must be resampled using a computationally intensive interpolation procedure to ensure they lie on the same discrete wavelength values prior to the final integration step. Due to this additional overhead, often the only computationally feasible approach for utilizing $\mathcal{P}_{\text{trad}}$ is to generate a large grid of model photometry for a discrete set of parameters (see § 2.3.1) before – rather than during – the actual SED fitting process.

2.3. SED Fitting

In addition to the variations and systematic uncertainties involved in generating SEDs discussed above (see also Conroy 2013), the methodologies used to explore the relevant regions of parameter space can differ greatly. Most fitting routines (e.g., Le PHARE; Arnouts et al. 1999; Ilbert et al. 2006) follow a “fixed”, grid-based template fitting approach to determine the GOF between model SEDs and observed photometry, constructing the full N-dimensional PDF for each object at a pre-defined resolution before deriving $P(z)$ by marginalizing over all other parameters and incorporating various possible priors (Moustakas et al. 2013). Newer, “adaptive” template fitting approaches (see, e.g., SATMC; Johnson et al. 2013) instead use MCMC fitting techniques in order to more efficiently determine best-fit physical parameters and better constrain the underlying posterior parameter distribution. And several photo-z codes (e.g., SOMz; Carrasco Kind & Brunner 2014b) opt out of the template fitting approach altogether to instead utilize (un)supervised machine learning approaches.¹⁰

In contrast to template fitting codes, which attempt to determine the best collection of *forward* mappings from model parameters to color space, “data-driven” machine learning methods instead attempt to directly determine the best *inverse* mapping from color space to redshift via a training set of multi-band photometry and corresponding spec-z’s. While these procedures are sensitive to the quality of the training sample and the specific training algorithm used, they have the advantage of being (relatively) model-independent. This inverse-mapping process, however, makes deriving uncertainties from and incorporating uncertainties into machine learning codes difficult (Carrasco Kind & Brunner 2014b). While both methods are useful, only template fitting-based methods will be discussed in this work.

2.3.1. Fixed (Grid-based) Template Fitting

The simplest (but often most computationally expensive) approach taken by most photo-z codes such as Le PHARE (Arnouts et al. 1999; Ilbert et al. 2006) to exploring multidimensional parameter spaces is a grid-based approach. For each parameter x_i , a discrete set of values $\{x_{i,1}, \dots, x_{i,m}\}$

¹⁰See Bishop (2006) for more information on various machine learning algorithms and Hildebrandt et al. (2010) for several examples of machine learning-based photo-z codes. See also Ménard et al. (2013).

spanning the range of interest are chosen. A collection of trial points is then drawn from the set of all possible combinations of these discrete subsets to create a multidimensional grid. This grid of points is then fit to each object to build up a model of the full N -dimensional $P(\vec{x}|\vec{F}_{\text{obs}})$ for each object at a predetermined resolution. Afterwards, marginalized PDFs can be created through a weighted sum

$$P(\vec{x}_I|\vec{F}_{\text{obs}}) \propto \int P(\vec{x}|\vec{F}_{\text{obs}})d\vec{x}_J \approx \sum_{\vec{x}_J} P(\vec{x}|\vec{F}_{\text{obs}}), \quad (31)$$

where \vec{x}_I are the parameters of interest and \vec{x}_J are the parameters to be marginalized over.

In many cases, however, it is desirable to modify the N -dimensional PDF with some aspect of prior knowledge. This can be done using Bayes’ Theorem, which describes the inference of a set of parameters Θ in a given model/hypothesis H for a set of data \mathbf{D} . Formally, this is

$$P(\Theta|\mathbf{D}, H) = \frac{P(\mathbf{D}|\Theta, H)P(\Theta|H)}{P(\mathbf{D}|H)}, \quad (32)$$

where $P(\Theta|\mathbf{D}, H)$ is the *posterior distribution* of Θ given \mathbf{D} , $P(\mathbf{D}|\Theta, H)$ is the *likelihood* of \mathbf{D} given Θ , $P(\Theta|H)$ is the *prior*, and $\mathcal{Z} \equiv P(\mathbf{D}|H)$ is the total *evidence* that the data is explained by the model.¹¹

Most often, model selection between two competing models H_0 and H_1 can be determined by calculating the relative ratio of their total evidence. Assuming that H_1 has an additional ΔN DOF (i.e. additional parameters) compared to H_0 , the relative likelihood ratio $R_{\Delta N}$ is (see also Akaike 1974)

$$R_{\Delta N} = R e^{-\Delta N}, \quad (33)$$

where $R_{\Delta N=0} \equiv R$ is often referred to as the Bayes Factor and defined as

$$R = \frac{P(H_1|\mathbf{D})}{P(H_0|\mathbf{D})} = \frac{P(\mathbf{D}|H_1)P(H_1)}{P(\mathbf{D}|H_0)P(H_0)} = \frac{\mathcal{Z}_1 P(H_1)}{\mathcal{Z}_0 P(H_0)}, \quad (34)$$

where most often $P(H_1)/P(H_0)$ is set to unity. Since calculation of the evidence is generally expensive and in many cases only a specific model and set of priors are being investigated, most often Bayes’ theorem is simply applied as

$$P(\Theta|\mathbf{D}) \propto P(\mathbf{D}|\Theta)P(\Theta). \quad (35)$$

This approach – taken by, e.g., ZEBRA (Feldmann et al. 2006) and iSEDfit Moustakas et al. (2013) – effectively allows us to “distort” the final (grid-based) PDF based on prior information (from, e.g.,

¹¹In our specific case, the posterior distribution $P(\Theta|\mathbf{D}) = P(\vec{x}|\vec{F})$ is the multi-dimensional PDF of the fitted parameters, $P(\mathbf{D}|\Theta) = P(\vec{F}|\vec{x})$ is the GOF-based PDF derived from comparing our model to data, $P(\vec{x})$ is the associated collection of priors on the fitted parameters (often taken from luminosity functions; Bolzonella et al. 2000), and we are specifically interested in marginalizing over $P(\vec{x}|\vec{F})$ to derive the 1-D redshift PDF $P(z|\vec{F})$.

luminosity functions, survey design, etc.) to derive a more accurate representation of the underlying PDF (see, e.g., Bolzonella et al. 2000).

While generally effective (Hildebrandt et al. 2010; Dahlen et al. 2013), grid-based approaches are subject to three major problems:

1. **Scale proportional to dimensionality of problem.** As the search space is created through some subset of all possible combinations of parameters, it increases multiplicatively with the number of dimensions to be probed and the desired “fineness” of each dimension of the grid. This makes it difficult to scale grid-based approaches up to higher dimensions or to finer resolutions without being forced to sacrifice accuracy elsewhere.
2. **Inefficient at probing region of interest.** Grid-based approaches are inefficient at locating and characterizing global minima. As the majority of global minima (used to derive the marginalized redshift PDFs) tend to be concentrated within certain regions of the N -dimensional parameter space, grid-based methods – which sample evenly and without regard to shape or topology – spend the majority of time for any given object ($\gtrsim 99\%$) sampling regions of extremely low probability. Thus, while they can capture the overall shape of the PDF, including degeneracies located in widely-separated regions of parameter space, they are particularly ill-suited for characterizing the areas around relevant probability maxima at high resolution.
3. **Fundamentally discretize continuous parameters.** Due to the nature of constructing a grid from a set of (quasi-)continuous parameters, most grid-based approaches actually discretize the space in a fundamental way, turning continuous parameters such as $E(B-V)$ into discrete, “representative” groups rather than a set of points drawn from a continuous distribution. This process is fundamentally akin to an implicit averaging, which may remove additional information and/or structure likely relevant to improving photo- z accuracy if the grid is not constructed at sufficient resolution.

In order to resolve some of these issues, new adaptive template fitting codes such as **GalMC** (Acquaviva et al. 2011) and **SATMC** (Johnson et al. 2013) have begun using MCMC fitting techniques in order to more efficiently determine best-fit physical parameters and better constrain the underlying posterior parameter distribution.

2.3.2. Adaptive (MCMC) Template Fitting

Unlike grid-based approaches, which sample parameter space evenly and apply likelihood-dependent weights afterwards, MCMC-based algorithms instead sample at a rate proportional to the PDF itself and weight every accepted trial point evenly. A standard search heuristic employed

by most MCMC codes is the Metropolis-Hastings (M-H) algorithm (Metropolis et al. 1953; Hastings 1970):

1. Draw a set of trial parameters \vec{x}_n from the neighborhood function¹² $q(\vec{x}|\vec{x}_{n-1})$.
2. Accept the new trial \vec{x}_n according to the likelihood ratio $\alpha = \min\left(1, \frac{P(\vec{x}_n|\vec{F})}{P(\vec{x}_{n-1}|\vec{F})} \frac{q(\vec{x}_{n-1}|\vec{x}_n)}{q(\vec{x}_n|\vec{x}_{n-1})}\right)$ between the two sets of parameters and the corresponding neighborhood functions. Otherwise, remain at \vec{x}_{n-1} .
3. Repeat for the next draw.

This procedure is used to guide several individual “chains” of related draws as they converge to and eventually begin sampling from the region of interest. Although the exact neighborhood function chosen is ultimately arbitrary, most often an N -dimensional multivariate-normal distribution $N(\vec{\mu}, \Sigma)$ is used, where $\vec{\mu} = \vec{x}_{n-1}$ is the mean vector (adjusted at each step) and $\Sigma = \sigma^2 \mathbf{I}$ (where \mathbf{I} is the identity matrix) is the covariance matrix.

As the performance of an MCMC-based algorithm during both the “burn-in” phase (i.e. the time necessary to reach a stable solution) and the period of time spent sampling the region of interest is sensitive to the size of neighborhood function relative to the search space, most often Σ is calculated in real time based on how well each chain has performed over some previous interval. For this approach, each component σ_i is taken to be the expectation value (i.e. the weighted average $\langle \vec{a} \rangle$) of the deviations of the previous number of N trials away from their expectation value,

$$\sigma_i = \langle (\vec{x}_{N,i} - \langle \vec{x}_{N,i} \rangle) (\vec{x}_{N,i} - \langle \vec{x}_{N,i} \rangle)^T \rangle, \quad (36)$$

where T is the transpose operator and $\vec{x}_{N,i}$ is the i th component of each set of parameters \vec{x} from the past N trials. This is then adjusted based on the average acceptance rate over the same interval until a target acceptance rate can be achieved.

Because MCMC-based algorithms sample at a rate approximately proportional to the PDF in a given region of interest, they are able to explore a large, N -dimensional space with far fewer function calls than grid-based approaches at finer resolution while scaling slowly with the dimensionality of the problem. As these function calls are often computationally expensive (e.g., $\mathcal{P}_{\text{trad}}$), such a feature is extremely useful.¹³

However, MCMC-based approaches are still subject to several issues:

¹²Also often referred to as a “proposal distribution”.

¹³Alternately, if the results of each trial are calculated at a pre-defined resolution and stored in memory (e.g., **SpeedyMC**; Acquaviva et al. 2012), MCMC-based approaches simply represent a more efficient way of traversing a grid to develop a model of the likelihood. See also § 3.

1. **Extremely sensitive to form of neighborhood function.** As the performance of MCMC-based algorithms is sensitive to the precise construction and implementation of the neighborhood function, effort must be spent either fine-tuning such a function by hand or calculating relevant quantities from the data in real time.
2. **Only samples locally.** Because MCMC-based algorithms reconstruct the PDF by simply counting the (final) number of accepted trials, only the relative shape of the region of interest can be recovered. As a result, for a multimodal distribution where the probability “peaks” are separated by distances much larger than the neighborhood function, the relative heights of the peaks cannot be recovered.
3. **Fails to generate fully independent draws.** MCMC codes do not give fully independent draws from the region of interest, but rather a convolution of the surrounding parameter space with the neighborhood function. To ensure fully independent draws, the individual chains must often be “thinned” by removing a subset (usually a majority) of trials from the region of interest to ensure appropriate randomness in sampling.
4. **Loses information from burn-in.** Since MCMC codes reconstruct the PDF by counting weighting all accepted trials uniformly, they are unable to include trials from the burn-in phase because the set of parameters are sensitive to the chains’ initial positions.
5. **Samples ineffectively during burn-in.** During the burn-in period, MCMC-based codes using an unmodified version of the M-H algorithm engage in a biased random walk throughout the space to the region of interest. In general, this process is highly inefficient compared to many other simple gradient-based minimization algorithms.

Efforts to improve on this methodology and alleviate these issues will be discussed in §3, while improvements to the general process of generating photometry and exploring parameter space will be discussed in §4.

2.4. Deriving PDFs from the SED Fitting Process

Although the fitting process is important, it is often not enough to simply take the best-fitting χ_{mod}^2 and the corresponding \vec{x}_{best} set of parameters. Instead, it is often more useful to utilize a collection of χ_{mod}^2 values and their corresponding \vec{x} 's to reconstruct the full probability distribution $P(\vec{x}_I | \vec{F}_{\text{obs}})$, where \vec{x}_I is a subset of the components of \vec{x} .

In the case of photo-z's, the ultimate goal is to derive $P(z | \vec{F}_{\text{obs}})$ marginalized over all other parameters included in the fit. This can be done in one of two ways:

1. **Monte Carlo.** Create a set of perturbed photometry \vec{F}'_{obs} where $F'_{\text{obs},i} = F_{\text{obs},i} + n_i \sigma_i$, where n_i is a random number drawn from a standard normal distribution. Refit \vec{F}'_{obs} to

derive a new \vec{x}'_{best} . Repeat this process N times to get a collection of best-fit parameters $\{\vec{x}_{\text{best},1}, \vec{x}_{\text{best},2}, \dots, \vec{x}_{\text{best},N}\}$. A marginalized distribution can then be constructed by creating N -dimensional histograms of the relevant parameters. For most machine learning codes, this is the only method available to derive uncertainties.

2. **Directly modelling the PDF.** During the process of locating $\chi^2_{\text{mod,best}}$, save a subset of the $\chi^2_{\text{mod}}(\vec{x}_n|\vec{F}_{\text{obs}})$ values and their corresponding \vec{x}_n 's from the total set of N trials. Depending on the sampling technique, these can then be combined (with their corresponding probabilities) to derive a model of the full or marginalized PDF of choice. This is most easily done using template fitting codes.

Ideally, both methods can be used as cross-checks for each other to verify whether the fitting procedure(s) and the corresponding PDF(s) are robust.

Fig. 11.— The redshift distribution of our mock catalog of $\sim 380,000$ COSMOS galaxies. The majority of galaxies are located at $z \lesssim 3.5$, although a handful extend out to $z \sim 6$.

3. Improving Pre-Existing Fitting Methodologies with BAD-Z

As discussed in §2, traditional template fitting methods generate new model photometry by performing a series of operations on a set of templates before convolving the final template with the relevant filters (i.e. $\mathcal{P}_{\text{trad}} = \mathcal{F}^z(\mathcal{M}(x))$). As this function call is expensive, most current approaches choose to pre-generate a large grid of model templates containing on the order of $\sim 10^{6-7}$ individual sets of photometry and then either fit the entire grid to each individual object (e.g., Le PHARE) or traverse the grid using an MCMC approach (e.g., SpeedyMC).

Since these fitting routines are designed to be applied to large sets of objects, such an approach is quite practical: pre-computing photometry from a large set of parameter combinations often saves orders of magnitude of computation time compared to repeatedly computing them in real time, especially given the number of objects usually involved. Without a cursory understanding of the nature of the parameter space (i.e., the general topology of the multidimensional $\chi^2(\vec{x})$ function/likelihood surface for a typical range of SEDs) this approach seems quite reasonable – grids are suitable as a “brute force” approach for a wide range of applications provided they are sampling finely enough, while MCMC algorithms tend to be robust for functions with a reasonably well-defined gradient in a sizeable area surrounding the minimum/maximum of interest.

While ultimately we wish to move away from reliance on any underlying grid in continuous

parameters (e.g., reddening via $E(B-V)$ or emission line strengths via \vec{b}), we first want to develop a more efficient way of traversing a pre-existing grid constructed as outlined in §2.2 to get a sense of how efficient these approaches can become. Our aim in this section is to develop an algorithm for which the number of trials for an object is approximately constant while also being much smaller than the total number of points in the entire grid (i.e. $N_{\text{trials}} \sim \text{constant} \ll N_{\text{grid}}$). Such a code would allow us to increase the accuracy of pre-existing codes without sacrificing additional computation time as long as an increasingly finely sampled grid can be stored in memory.

3.1. Generating a Realistic Mock Catalog

In order to develop an improved method of traversing the grid, we need to first understand the nature of the parameter space we are hoping to explore. To avoid possible issues caused by template mismatch (as compared to the full range of observed galaxy SEDs) and other possible systematic effects, we decide to explore the parameter space based on a mock catalog of galaxies constructed from real data using the same grid we hope to later test.

We begin the construction of our mock catalog using the high-quality photometry (~ 30 bands) available in the COSMOS field. Photo- z 's are derived using the grid-based code `Le PHARE`, which utilizes a grid with the following specifications:

1. $N_z = 601$: The grid is constructed spanning the redshift range $z = 0-6$ in steps of $\Delta z = 0.01$.
2. $N_{\text{template}} = 31$: The galaxy template set used includes 8 elliptical templates and 11 spiral templates (constructed by linearly interpolating between the Polletta et al. (2007) templates), supplemented with 12 starburst (SB) templates constructed from Bruzual & Charlot (2003) SPS models assuming exponentially declining SFHs with ages ranging from 3 to 0.03 Gyr. See Figure 6.
3. $N_{\text{emline}} = 3$: Only a single template including Ly α , O[II], H β , O[III], and H α is used. This is added to each template prior to applying reddening effects according to $\{0.5, 1.0, 2.0\}$ times the scaling relations outlined in Ilbert et al. (2009). See Figure 7.
4. $N_{\text{dust}} = 5$: The dust curves used include dust curves from the Small Magellanic Cloud (SMC; Prevot et al. 1984), Large Magellanic Cloud (LMC; Fitzpatrick 1986), the Milky Way (MW; Seaton 1979; Allen 1976), and SB galaxies (Calzetti et al. 2000). See Figure 8.
5. $N_{E(B-V)} = 9$: Each template is allowed $E(B-V)$ values of $\{0, 0.05, 0.1, 0.15, 0.2, 0.25, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5\}$.

After correcting for zero-point offsets using the spec- z comparison sample, a subset of the grid is then fit to each object and marginalized over to derive the redshift PDF for each individual object (Ilbert et al. 2009). The best-fitting template, reddening law, $E(B-V)$, and scaling factor are then

Fig. 12.— The transmission functions of the 12 filters used in this study: UV_c (light blue), u_c (blue), g_c (light green), u (green), g (pink), r (red), i (light orange), z (orange), Y (light purple), Y_w (purple), J_w (yellow), and H_w (brown). The extended UV–NIR coverage allows us to test the performance of our photo- z algorithms given a wide range of wavelength information.

saved. The redshift PDF is then regenerated to higher resolution and the median of the resulting PDF is saved. The emission line contributions are marginalized over during the fitting process.

From an initial sample of ~ 2 million galaxies in the COSMOS field, we implement a series of H -band cuts as a function of intrinsic size (measured by the half-light radius R_h) designed to mimic the future **WFIRST (Wide-Field InfraRed Space Telescope)** sample, which are listed in Table 1. This left us with $\sim 20\%$ of the sample, or $\sim 380,000$ galaxies spanning a redshift range from $z = 0$ to ~ 3.5 , including a handful of objects up to $z \sim 6$ (see Figure 11). Using the parameters that **Le PHARE** derived/saved for each galaxy, we create a collection of model galaxy templates using the same procedure outlined above (i.e. $\mathcal{M}(\vec{x})$). As the emission line contributions were not recorded (i.e. $\vec{b} = \vec{0}$), we decide not to simulate them to simplify the nature of our tests ($N_{\text{dim}} = 5 \rightarrow 4$).

We convolve these templates with a set of 12 filters designed to mimic the wavelength ranges probed by the future **CASTOR (the Cosmological Advanced Survey Telescope for Optical and UV Research; UV_cu_cg_c)** and **WFIRST (Y_wJ_wH_w)** space missions supplemented with ground-based photometry (*ugrizY*). These provide a wide wavelength range to detect spectral features, as shown

Fig. 13.— Photometry (in magnitudes) in each band for all objects in the catalog as a function of redshift, with 50%, 70%, 90%, 95%, and 99% contours overlotted. 5σ upper limits are denoted by dashed red lines. Our mock catalog spans a decently large range in magnitude in all available bands. The impact of our *WFIRST* cuts (Table 1) can be seen most clearly in the bottom right two panels.

in Figure 12.

These photometric fluxes are then jittered according to the expected background noise levels based on the depth of the imaging in each band¹⁴ to create the final mock catalog. The distribution of photometry (in magnitudes) as a function of redshift in each of the filters is shown in Figure 13. To avoid complications arising from upper limits (see § 2.1), we opt to leave the final computed photometry in flux space during the actual fitting process.

¹⁴This calculation does not include error from shot noise from galaxy photons, which is expected to be on the order of $\sim 2\%$ at the 3σ detection limit.

Fig. 14.— The distribution of reduced- χ_{base}^2 values across our sample, calculated by deriving the corresponding χ_{min}^2 values for each of the original templates used when generating the initial photometry. As expected, the median of the distribution is approximately 1. In addition, the maximum reduced- χ_{base}^2 values do not exceed 4, providing an easy test as to whether objects in our sample are being well fit by our new photo-z code.

In addition, we also compute a baseline GOF value for each set of mock photometry (χ_{base}^2) by determining the χ^2 value between the original and final mock photometry. The distribution for the entire dataset is shown in Figure 14. This allows us to see the extent to which our errors altered the original GOF while also providing a check on the overall quality of the best fits determined by our code(s). If a code is performing optimally, the derived χ_{obj}^2 for an object should always satisfy the condition $\chi_{\text{obj}}^2 \leq \chi_{\text{base}}^2$.

In other words, an ideal photo-z code should always be finding either (1) the “correct” solution or (2) an “incorrect” (physical) one that is a better fit to the data. This is not always true in practice, especially in cases where the best-fitting redshift has been regenerated to a higher resolution than the corresponding grid spacing. In addition, while being able to find the “best” match to the data is a desirable feature of an effective fitting routine, it is not strictly necessary – as long as the general region *around* the best fit is probed sufficiently well, a given algorithm should still be able to derive accurate redshift PDFs. This point is discussed in more detail in §3.4.

3.2. Characterizing the Parameter Space

Computing photo- z 's involve two general types of parameters: discrete (galaxy, emission, and dust “templates”, etc.) and continuous (redshift, reddening, etc.). Many of the most effective algorithms for high-dimensional optimization problems (e.g., Levenberg-Marquardt; Levenberg 1944; Marquardt 1963), however, only function properly for a (quasi-)continuous set of parameters. In order to investigate whether these algorithms can be incorporated in some way into the fitting process (since they are often orders of magnitude more efficient at finding minima than a grid-based approach), we decide to first explore a reduced 2-D z - $E(B-V)$ subspace for a given set of templates (§ 3.2.1) before moving onto the full 4D parameter space (§ 3.2.2).

3.2.1. Exploring Structure in 2D Redshift-Reddening Subspace

Due to the constrained nature of minimizing $\mathcal{P}(z, E(B-V)|\vec{a}, \vec{c})$ as formulated above (again, we have set $\vec{b} = 0$) where the quantities are both non-negative and bounded ($0 \leq z_{\min} \leq z \leq z_{\max}$; $0 \leq E(B-V)_{\min} \leq E(B-V) \leq E(B-V)_{\max}$), we need to modify our GOF function in order to effectively utilize a variety of generalized minimization algorithms. In particular, we need to introduce penalties for exploring non-allowed regions of parameter space, while at the same time introducing a gradient encouraging the algorithm to quickly arrive at and begin sampling from the allowed region. We experiment with several simple forms of penalty functions and find the best performance for several common algorithms including Levenberg-Marquardt, Nelder-Mead (Nelder & Mead 1965), and Powell’s Method (Powell 1964) still results in a decent fraction of time ($\gtrsim 25\%$) spent sampling non-allowed regions before converging to and consistently sampling from the allowed regions.

By contrast, we find that a constrained minimization algorithm such as COBYLA (**C**onstrained **O**ptimization **BY** **L**inear **A**pproximation; Powell 1994) samples relatively efficiently in most cases. Since these algorithms do not require additional penalty functions and/or fine tuning while giving comparable performance, we opt to use them to probe the reduced 2D subspace for several objects from our mock catalog.

In order to investigate the likely possibility of multiple, widely-separated minima within the subspace, we supplement this approach with a simple version of basin-hopping (Wales & Doye 1997). Basin-hopping is an iterative stochastic metaheuristic (i.e. an additional heuristic superimposed on top of a pre-existing search heuristic) designed to probe spaces with a few deep but widely separated degeneracies that acts on a given minimization routine as follows:

1. Given the position $\vec{x}_{\text{start},i}$ of the last accepted minimum, randomly jump to a new coordinate $\vec{x}_{\text{start},n}$ based on a given neighborhood function $q(\vec{x}|\vec{x}_{\text{start}})$. As with MCMC approaches, this is often chosen to be an N -dimensional multivariate Gaussian with some arbitrary stepsize Σ that can either be calculated in real-time based on past performance or declared *a priori*.

2. From $\vec{x}_{\text{start},n}$, use a chosen minimization algorithm to find the nearest minimum $\vec{x}_{\text{min},n}$.
3. Replace $\vec{x}_{\text{start},i \rightarrow i+1}$ with the new coordinates $\vec{x}_{\text{min},n}$ with a probability based on the M-H criterion, i.e. $\min \left[\frac{P(\vec{x}_{\text{min},n})}{P(\vec{x}_{\text{start},i})}, 1 \right]$.
4. Repeat from step 1 for either a set number of iterations or until the process converges to the same minimum (based on repeat runs).
5. Select the global minimum from the collection of all accepted minima $\{\vec{x}_{\text{start},i}\}$.

This procedure is similar to an MCMC algorithm, where instead of accepting/rejecting every step at each new trial location we instead run a specific minimization routine starting from that location and accept/reject our result at the end.

In our particular case, we wish to avoid any procedural fine-tuning due to a given form of the chosen form for $q(\vec{x})$ and so opt to utilize a uniform prior over the entire z and $E(B-V)$ interval and a fixed number of N_{hops} runs. This is the equivalent of stochastically sampling (using our specific chosen minimizer) over the entire space of interest. While this is not an efficient way to locate the global minimum, it should be sufficient to uncover general features of the space that will help build up our intuition.

The output for one such object given the “correct” galaxy and dust templates is shown in Figure 15. We find the total number of trials required to find the global minimum in this subspace is relatively small, with $N_{\text{trials}} \lesssim 1500$. This corresponds to $\sim 30\%$ of the size of the corresponding $z-E(B-V)$ grid, albeit sampled at arbitrary rather than fixed resolution. As N_{trials} scales approximately linearly with N_{hops} , the true efficiency for an algorithm tailored to the specifics of this space (using, e.g., an effective neighborhood function) would likely be higher. As a result, we find that running a constrained stochastic minimization procedure for every combination of discrete parameters by itself is a least a factor of 3 more efficient at finding (albeit not characterizing) the global minimum than a standard grid search.

In addition, we observe several notable features present in our map. The most apparent is the commonly observed redshift-reddening degeneracy (i.e., “red” objects may either be dusty or at higher redshift), which traces out a high-probability valley within parameter space that COBYLA converges to in multiple instances. However, several competing minima are also present even in this reduced subspace. While the relative sampling frequency and general distribution of trials around each minimum indicates that most of these have probabilities significantly lower than that of the global minimum and occupy less relative area within the parameter space, they still appear to serve as a significant confounding factor given the number of trials that converged to these locations.

These features are also not limited to a specific galaxy-dust template combination – for a similar procedure computed using a similar but slightly mismatched galaxy template-dust curve combination, we observe many similar features. For extremely mismatched templates, however (e.g.,

Fig. 15.— A COBYLA minimization run using stochastic basinhopping ($N_{\text{hops}} = 10$) on a 2-D z - $E(B-V)$ slice for a sample object at $[z, E(B-V)] = [2.2221, 0.2]$ given the “correct” underlying galaxy-dust template combination. Each trial point is plotted and colored according to the corresponding $\log \chi^2$ value. Based on the number of runs which terminated at locations other than the global minimum (red squares), we can infer that the space is relatively “bumpy”, and is filled with a significant number of minima surrounding the global best-fit value (cyan star). While most of these have probability densities substantially smaller than the global minimum and occupy less relative area (based on the amount of sampling around each minimum), they are still a significant confounding factor during the minimization process.

trying to fit an elliptical to a slightly reddened spiral), we instead find the algorithm repeatedly terminates at boundary locations (i.e. grid edges) such as $[z, E(B-V)] = [0, 0]$.

Together, these findings suggest that the full 4-D parameter space likely has at least some of the following properties:

1. One main global minimum surrounded by several competing minima that occupy sizeable (but not overwhelming) regions of parameter space. As a result, the space directly in the area of the global minimum and other notable degeneracies (e.g. confusion over the Lyman and Balmer breaks) are likely quite “bumpy”.

2. A significant likelihood volume contained across and/or at the opposing ends of the redshift-reddening degeneracy.
3. A series of fitting artifacts (i.e. edge effects) due to highly mismatched templates that should lead to “ridges” within the corresponding region of parameter space. Taken together, these will likely have negligible probability, but unfortunately will probably occupy a non-negligible region of parameter space that will need to be avoided.

3.2.2. *The Full Redshift-Galaxy-Dust-Reddening Search*

To test these inferences, we now move on to exploring the full 4-D parameter space involving not only bounded parameters but fundamentally discrete ones. Because most minimization algorithms determine their next trial by probing changes at some small δx_i value away from the original parameters, this constitutes a significant issue.

There are several possible solutions one might implement. First, one could set the associated step size in the discrete parameters to be the spacing between the templates themselves (i.e. $\Delta x_i = 1$, incrementing over the associated templates). Although this would ensure all trials were valid, tuning a continuous stepping procedure into a discrete one (i.e. incorporating discontinuous derivatives) is quite tricky to implement properly.

Alternately, one could attempt to make the discrete parameters (quasi-)continuous through some type of interpolation process. This has the advantage of allowing the minimization algorithm to remain unchanged, albeit at the cost of introducing (possibly large) approximation errors.

We test the latter method using a simple 2D linear interpolation between corresponding model templates (since z and $E(B-V)$ are already continuous). Defining a generalized distance metric,

$$d_p = \left[\sum_i (\Delta x_i)^p \right]^{1/p}, \quad (37)$$

we derive $d_{p=2}$ (i.e. radial) distances between the corresponding four closest template combinations for a given $[\vec{a}, \vec{c}]$ coordinate. We then apply a weight to each template combination inversely proportional to the normalized distance from the trial point ($w_{\vec{a}, \vec{c}} \propto 1/d_{p=2}$, where $\sum_{\vec{a}, \vec{c}} w_{\vec{a}, \vec{c}} = 1$).

Unfortunately, when this method was applied to the same set of algorithms mentioned above, it failed to locate the best-fit solution(s) in almost all cases, instead converging to many spurious solutions with large χ^2 values. This indicates that either (1) our linear approximation between constructed templates is a poor approximation, or (2) that the parameter space is extremely bumpy and/or multimodal, both of which are plausible.

To figure out which possibility is the larger contributing factor, we construct a direct map of our higher-dimensional parameter space. Such maps should also provide additional insight/intuition

Fig. 16.— Results from our 4-D maps of parameter space for three sample objects (left to right). **Top panels:** Marginalized $P(z)$ distributions for each object. Individual grid points are plotted as black dots, with a cubic spline fit shown with the solid red line. The location of the peak is marked by the dashed red line. In all cases the $P(z)$ distribution is narrow and well-defined. **Middle panels:** The χ^2 values of individual minima (for 12-band photometry) as a function of the $d_{p=2}$ distance from the global minimum. Each plot shows most minima within $\Delta z \sim 0.5$ (at large distances d_{grid} per 20 units corresponds to a $\Delta z \sim 0.1$). The sheer number of minima indicates the region around the global minimum is indeed quite bumpy (see Figure 15). However, since most minima are at χ^2 values significantly higher than the global, they have an extremely small impact on the marginalized $P(z)$ distributions (top panels). **Bottom panels:** The probability (normalized to 1) that a random trial point on the grid will reach a specific minimum, shown as a function of $d_{p=2}$ distance from the global minimum. While the global minimum is a (far) better fit than most competing minima (middle panels), they occupy an extremely large area of parameter space and can confound local and/or gradient-based minimization algorithms as a result. The impact of degeneracies at widely separated distances from the global minimum (clusters of large minima at $d_{\text{grid}} \gtrsim 100$) as well as edge effects (extended “furrows” at $d_{\text{grid}} \gtrsim 300$) can also be seen.

into the general topology/features of the full 4-D space that we might have missed with our analysis of individual 2-D slices.

Using a finely spaced grid of ~ 2 million elements (identical to the one described in § 3.1 except with twice the redshift resolution and again excluding emission lines), we calculate the χ^2 value at every trial point. This allows us to determine the locations and depths (i.e. probabilities) for competing minima as a function of $d_{p=2}$ distance (normalized to the resolution in each dimension) from the global minimum. Because the size of the redshift grid is much larger than the other dimensions ($N_z \sim 1200$), this distance tends to be dominated by differences in redshift such that $d_{\text{grid}}/20$ corresponds to a Δz of ~ 0.1 .

To determine the relative size of each minimum, we had each point on the grid follow the surrounding gradient until it located the closest corresponding minimum. More precisely, for each grid point \vec{x}_i , we located the $2^4 = 16$ surrounding $\chi^2(\vec{x}_j)$ values, saved the \vec{x}_j value corresponding to the minimum χ^2 value, and then updated the locations of each point. If a point was already located in a local minimum (i.e. $\chi^2(\vec{x}_j) > \chi^2(\vec{x}_i)$ for all surrounding \vec{x}_j values), its position remained unchanged. We ran this procedure iteratively until the map converged, then recorded the number of trial points occupying each local minimum.

To understand how this underlying structure corresponds to the output $P(z)$ distribution, we marginalized over all trials to derive the redshift PDF (see § 2.3.1). Together, these pieces of information not only inform us about the approximate general distribution, area, depth, and behavior of minima within the 4-D parameter space, but also how all this structure affects the final marginalized distribution of interest. The results for three sample objects are plotted in Figure 16.

We find that many of the general features we predicted based on the results from § 3.2.1 still hold in the larger space: the regions around the global minimum are relatively bumpy (middle panels), the redshift-reddening degeneracy appears to occupy a significant region of parameter space (bottom panels), and edge effects occupy a non-negligible region of parameter space (bottom panels). However, most of this substructure does not appear in the final redshift PDF (top panels). Furthermore, many of these features are more extreme than we expected – not only does the full 4-D space appear to contain hundreds to thousands of local minima, but degenerate regions a significant distance away from the global minimum actually occupy a larger region of parameter space.

3.3. Creating an Effective Photo-z Algorithm

Based on our results from § 3.2, we find that the parameter space we intend to probe is filled with intricate substructure not visible in the final marginalized redshift PDF (Figure 16). In particular, while only the region directly surrounding the global minimum contains most of the $P(z)$ signal (top panels), the presence of hundreds to thousands of local minima along with large degenerate regions fill the majority of the parameter space for any individual object. It is thus no surprise that our constrained minimization approach outlined in the beginning of § 3.2.2 behaved poorly: the general

topology of the photo-z parameter space seems designed to thwart such an approach.

A specific fitting routine thus must be able to function effectively on a space with the following properties:

1. For each object, there are likely $\gtrsim 100$ minima. These are not only located in the immediate vicinity of the global minimum, but are also common in degenerate regions and more generally scattered throughout the space.
2. Although most minima are a significantly worse fit than the global minimum, they occupy a larger area. In particular, minima within degenerate regions occupy a much larger fraction of parameter space than the region around the global minimum.
3. Asymmetries in model generation lead to gradient “valleys” that terminate at grid edges.

Although the third condition is intrinsic to the model generating process (but see §4.2), we attempt to develop an algorithm that addresses the first two. This leads to three main key features a successful algorithm should possess:

1. **Should not be overly “greedy”.** Even with multiple restarts (either random or learned), the probability of finding the global minimum through any “greedy” minimization algorithm that relies solely on the surrounding gradient (e.g., Levenberg-Marquardt) is $\lesssim 1\%$.
2. **Should not rely on local sampling.** As degenerate regions occupy a large fraction of parameter space, algorithms that only sample locally (i.e., according to a neighborhood function) are likely to get caught in these regions. This would make standard MCMC implementations difficult, necessitating more sophisticated algorithms such as those used in Johnson et al. (2013). It also suggests that swarm intelligence-based methods will likely be more successful.
3. **Should be robust to “bumpy” spaces.** Due to the numerous shallow minima that are present in the regions of interest and more generally throughout the space, an effective algorithm should take advantage of a smoothing metaheuristic that enables it to find the region surrounding the global minimum.

More generally, our algorithm should be able to sample the space effectively (i.e. proportional to the probability) so that it can quickly and efficiently reconstruct the redshift PDF to high accuracy.

The recently published `emcee` (Foreman-Mackey et al. 2013) code, a swarm intelligence implementation of a standard MCMC approach, contains almost all of the desired properties outlined above. In brief, `emcee` simultaneously evolves an ensemble of N jumpers where the proposal distribution for the n th jumper at position \vec{x}_n is based on the current locations of the other $N - 1$ jumpers (i.e. the complementary ensemble). A new trial point at some iteration i is chosen by

“leapfrogging” or “bouncing” over a random jumper \vec{x}_m chosen from the complementary ensemble such that

$$\vec{x}_{n,i+1} = \vec{x}_{n,i} + y (\vec{x}_{n,i} - \vec{x}_m), \quad (38)$$

where y is a random variable drawn from the symmetric proposal distribution

$$g(y) \propto \frac{1}{\sqrt{y}}, \quad \frac{1}{a} < y < a, \quad (39)$$

with a an adjustable scale parameter most often set to 2. The new proposed position is then accepted with probability

$$q = \min \left(1, y^{N_{\text{dim}}-1} \frac{P(\vec{x}_{n,i+1})}{P(\vec{x}_{n,i})} \right). \quad (40)$$

These series of steps are then repeated for each jumper in the full ensemble in series before beginning a new set of trials.

In essence, rather than spawning several “chains” that each sample according to M-H from a neighborhood function, `emcee` instead spawns a (much larger) group of “jumpers” who each sample according to M-H from their immediate overall distribution in parameter space rather than any individual jumper’s local neighborhood. Furthermore, eliminating the neighborhood function decreases the fine-tuning required to implement this method while also ensuring that every trial is nearly independent, solving a number of issues raised in § 2.3.2. For our purposes then, `emcee` gives all the benefits inherent in an MCMC-driven approach while eliminating the majority of the drawbacks.

However, although the general implementation outlined above is powerful for sampling from a bumpy space around the region of interest, it will still be relatively inefficient during the burn-in phase. In conjunction with the extreme bumpiness inherent to this space, the “burn-in problem” posed in § 2.3.2 becomes even more pressing: how can an algorithm navigate through this parameter space to find the relevant region(s) as quickly as possible?

Simulated annealing is a metaheuristic designed to assist searches where the goal is to find the global minimum in a bumpy and often significantly multimodal space. The overall method involves imposing a global temperature on either the entire space (the standard implementation) or individual samplers/regions (as in parallel tempering; see Johnson et al. 2013) that distorts the shape of the space such that

$$P(\vec{x}) \rightarrow [P(\vec{x})]^{T_0/T(t)}, \quad (41)$$

where $T(t)$ is the temperature as a function of time and T_0 is an arbitrary scale factor that we will take to be 1 for the remainder of this paper.

At $T > T_0$, “bad” jumps become more likely, allowing an algorithm additional stochasticity while sampling. As a result, it is able to explore more of the search space in the hopes of finding the region around the global minimum. At $T < T_0$, bad jumps instead become less likely, reducing stochasticity. This makes the algorithm progressively more similar to a greedy minimization algorithm constrained to only move in the direction of the gradient. Ideally, this forces the algorithm to find a more optimal solution once it reaches the general region of interest.

Fig. 17.— χ^2 as a function of position of a 1D component of a sample 4D function designed to broadly mimic the features of our photo- z space described in §3.3. The underlying quadratic component is filled with numerous bumps with significant height, although the global minimum is still by far the best fit (central inset).

Fig. 18.— Individual trials plotted as a function of position in terms of χ^2 (left; central region inset) and $P = e^{-\frac{1}{2}\chi^2}$ (right). The dense sampling in the regions surrounding the global minimum show that the algorithm is sampling effectively.

To test whether that this approach will improve burn-in performance in the region we are hoping to explore, we investigated the performance of simulated annealing-driven `emcee`-based algorithm on the sample function shown in Figure 17 designed to mimic the overall properties of the photo- z parameter space we observed in § 3.2.2. Using an ensemble of 250 jumpers, a default scalefactor $a = 2$, a starting temperature $T_{\text{start}} = 2.5$, and a change in temperature $\Delta T = 0.01$ per run, we verified that not only was this combined algorithm able to effectively locate/characterize the region of interest (Figure 18), but that the performance at both low and high T was important in locating the global minimum (Figure 19).

Although this approach is effective, characterizing the general region at high enough resolution to derive $P(z)$ is an issue.¹⁵ A straightforward approach (and the one we take) is to only run the initial simulated annealing-driven `emcee` algorithm during the burn-in phase to locate the global minimum, then re-spawn an ensemble of walkers in an N -dimensional multivariate Gaussian distribution around the best value that samples according to the “vanilla” `emcee` algorithm.¹⁶ After discarding an initial fraction of trials (to ensure appropriate random sampling; see also Foreman-Mackey et al. 2013), the remaining one can be used to reconstruct the full N -dimensional PDF.

¹⁵As simulated annealing distorts the likelihood over the course of the run, sampling in the region of interest is additionally biased and cannot be reconstructed using the methods described in § 2.3.2.

¹⁶As mentioned in § 2.3.2, in almost all cases MCMC-based methods have a difficult time effectively characterizing multimodal spaces. In particular, the sampling efficiency of `emcee` rapidly declines when applied to multi-modal surfaces, especially when the modes are sharply peaked Foreman-Mackey et al. (2013). While respawning the ensemble of jumpers around the minimum will by default miss truly multimodal $P(z)$ ’s, it is chosen as a compromise to give a slightly biased view of the true $P(z)$ rather than completely undersampling and/or mischaracterizing it.

Fig. 19.— The likelihood probed by each individual jumper as a function of the temperature, with the transition temperature $T = 1$ indicated in red. The majority of jumpers that find their way towards locations closest to the global best-fit *value* occur after $T < 1$, while a good proportion of jumpers find their way to the general *region* while $T > 1$.

Using these results, we develop a photo-z code, **BAD-Z** (**B**ouncing and **A**nnealing **D**riven **R**edshifts (**Z**)), which functions as follows:

1. Initialize J jumpers on an arbitrary N -dimensional input grid drawn from a uniform distribution.
2. Start a simulated annealing-driven run with a given set of T_{start} and ΔT per run values to find the region of the global minimum.
3. Spawn a new distribution of J jumpers in an N -dimensional multivariate Gaussian with some fractional spread in each dimension σ_{frac} around the trial with the highest likelihood from the previous simulated annealing-driven run.
4. Start a new run using the standard M-H algorithm (i.e. $T(t) = 1$) for an additional N_{MCMC} number of ensemble trials.

5. After discarding an initial fraction f_{disc} of trials from the new run, use all the remaining accepted trials to reconstruct the final PDF.

BAD-Z is written entirely in C and parallelized using `openmp`.

3.4. Comparison with Grid-Based Code

To establish an appropriate comparison for our results, we code up **GRIPEZ** (**GRI**d-based **Photometric Estimation of Redshifts (Z)**), a grid-based counterpart to BAD-Z also in C. **GRIPEZ** works exactly as outlined in § 2.3.1, using the exact same input grid of photometry as BAD-Z.

We run both **GRIPEZ** and BAD-Z on the mock photometric catalog described in § 3.1 using the same grid described in § 3.2.2. This again possesses the following properties:

1. $N_z = 1201$: Probes $z = 0-6$ in steps of $\Delta z = 0.005$.
2. $N_{\text{template}} = 31$: Includes 8 elliptical templates and 11 spiral templates derived from Polletta et al. (2007), supplemented with 12 SB templates constructed from Bruzual & Charlot (2003) SPS models with ages ranging from 3 to 0.03 Gyr.
3. $N_{\text{dust}} = 5$: Includes dust curves from the SMC (Prevot et al. 1984), LMC (Fitzpatrick 1986), MW (Seaton 1979; Allen 1976), and SB galaxies (Calzetti et al. 2000).
4. $N_{E(B-V)} = 9$: Allows for $E(B-V)$ values of $\{0, 0.05, 0.1, 0.15, 0.2, 0.25, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5\}$.

For **GRIPEZ**, we fit the entire grid to each individual object, a process that involves a total of $\sim 1.6 \times 10^6$ trials per object.

For BAD-Z, we instead traverse this grid utilizing an ensemble with $N_{\text{jumpers}} = 150$, $a = 2$, $T_{\text{start}} = 3.0$, ΔT per run = 0.03, $\sigma_{\text{frac}} = 0.15$, $N_{\text{MCMC}} = 200$ (excluding the re-initialization process), and $f_{\text{disc}} = 0.4$. Note that this is a *conservative* choice of parameters that leads to a total of 45150 trials (2.7% of the full grid) per object (i.e., 301 ensemble runs), of which only 18000 (40% of all trials, 1.1% of the full grid) are used in the reconstruction of the final PDF. An example run for an individual object in our mock catalog is shown in Figure 20.

Using the reconstructed $P(z)$ for each individual object, we classify the best-fitting redshift as the median of the distribution z_{med} along with 1σ errors. The 2-D distributions of input redshifts z_{in} versus fitted redshifts z_{fit} for both methods are shown in Figure 21. Not only is BAD-Z $\gtrsim 40-50$ times more efficient than **GRIPEZ**, but it is also able to more accurately capture the underlying redshift PDF and avoid common low-redshift degeneracies (e.g., the redshift reddening degeneracy observed around $z \sim 0.6$).¹⁷

¹⁷We achieve similar results using redshift estimates derived from the peak of each redshift PDF z_{peak} , albeit with

Fig. 20.— **Top left:** The minimum $\log \text{reduced-}\chi^2$ located within the ensemble of jumpers ($N_{\text{jumpers}} = 150$) after each ensemble run ($N_{\text{runs}} = 301$) for an object from our mock catalog. In this specific case, BAD-Z converges to the best-fit set of parameters \vec{x}_{best} after $\sim 60\%$ of the simulated-annealing driven portion, and relocates it relatively quickly after the jumpers have respawned for the vanilla `emcee`-based portion. **Top right:** As the top left panel, but for the best-fit redshift z_{best} . Similar behavior can be seen, although now small perturbations away from z_{best} are visible. **Bottom left:** The best-fit model photometry (blue circles) plotted against the observed photometry (black circles with red error bars). For clarity, the model photometry has been slightly shifted from the observed photometry. The observed agreement between the two sets of points again indicates the overall quality of the final fit(s). **Bottom right:** The redshift PDF of the resulting `emcee`-based run for the final 40% of all trials (120 ensemble runs) as a function of time, with an increasing number of ensemble runs used to construct the PDF from blue to red. As we are consistently probing the area directly around \vec{x}_{best} (see top left), BAD-Z is able to effectively reconstruct the underlying PDF using 18,000 independent trials.

Fig. 21.— The distribution of input redshifts z_{in} versus fitted median redshifts z_{fit} (70%, 95%, and 99% contours plotted) for GRIPEZ (black) and BAD-Z (red) using a grid of ~ 2 million elements (§ 3.4) at $z \leq 3.2$. The marginalized distribution of fractional redshift error $\eta \equiv |z_{\text{fit}} - z_{\text{in}}| / (1 + z_{\text{in}})$ is shown in the upper left inset, with the usual threshold for “catastrophic errors” ($\eta_{\text{cat}} = 0.15$) indicated as dashed red lines. Not only is BAD-Z $\gtrsim 40$ times more efficient than GRIPEZ at exploring the pre-computed grid of model photometry, it is also able to more accurately capture the underlying redshift PDF and avoid degeneracies while providing similar levels of overall accuracy.

In addition to being significantly more efficient while providing similar (possibly improved) levels of accuracy, we can also investigate the ability of BAD-Z to find “optimal” ($\chi_{\text{fit}}^2 / \chi_{\text{base}}^2 \leq 1$) and “reasonable” ($\chi_{\text{fit}}^2 / \chi_{\text{base}}^2 \leq 5$) fits using our χ_{base}^2 metric. We find that BAD-Z is quite effective at finding good fits to the data, locating optimal fits in $\sim 55\%$ of cases and reasonable ones in $\sim 90\%$ (Figure 22). As the resulting redshifts are accurate in the majority of fitted objects (Figure 21), this indicates that even in cases where BAD-Z fails to find the “best” fit to the data, it still manages

slightly larger scatter and intrinsic bias.

Fig. 22.— The distribution of $\chi_{\text{fit}}^2/\chi_{\text{base}}^2$ (cumulative distribution inset), plotted in log space for clarity. The majority of our best fits ($\sim 55\%$; green dashed lines) are “optimal” fits such that $\chi_{\text{fit}}^2/\chi_{\text{base}}^2 \leq 1.0$ (i.e. the best model fit better than the “correct” one), while almost all ($\sim 90\%$; red dashed lines) are “reasonable” fits such that $\chi_{\text{fit}}^2/\chi_{\text{base}}^2 \leq 5.0$.

to probe the surrounding region to high enough accuracy that the marginalized $P(z)$ distribution gives accurate predictions.

In summary, by understanding the general topology of the relevant photo- z likelihood surface seen by a specific grid of pre-computed model photometry, we are able to design an algorithm that substantially outperforms traditional grid-based codes while retaining similar levels of accuracy. Our `emcee`-based, simulated annealing-driven method `BAD-Z` performs extremely well on the bumpy, degeneracy-dominated surface in most cases, performing well in $> 90\%$ of cases while still giving accurate redshift estimates to over 99% of the objects tested. `BAD-Z` thus illustrates the power inherent in the general methodology outlined in this section in addition to being an extremely effective and competitive photo- z code.

4. Developing a New Photo-z Framework

While our results for BAD-Z are promising, the algorithm still suffers from three major issues intrinsic to the methodology itself:

1. **Constrained to a grid.** Due to computational constraints, BAD-Z is still most effective when traversing a precomputed grid. This often establishes a computationally-limited (rather than data-limited or model-limited) accuracy to which one can probe continuous changes in, e.g., emission line strengths, reddening, and redshift based on the relative size/resolution of the grid that can be stored in memory.
2. **Generates model asymmetrically.** BAD-Z treats reddening (and emission lines) asymmetrically (i.e. only additive), which limits the available range of useable templates and leads to edge effects that manifest during the model-fitting process (see §3.2). While this is not intrinsic to the model generating process itself, it is often not taken into account.
3. **Only probes regions surrounding the global minimum.** Our emcee-based algorithm is still subject to the limitations inherent to MCMC sampling and cannot locate and/or distinguish between widely separated probability peaks that are a fundamental part of the photo-z parameter space. While BAD-Z might give better PDFs/redshift estimates on average for galaxies with only one main $P(z)$ peak, it is hampered in its ability to identify galaxies particularly susceptible to being catastrophically misfit.

We deal with each of these issues in turn. In §4.1, we develop a new “perturbative” model photometry-generating process $\mathcal{P}_{\text{ptrb}}$ that moves away from a discrete grid to instead incorporate a continuous range emission line strengths (\vec{b}), reddenings ($E(B-V)$), and redshifts (z). Using this approach, in §4.2 we introduce the framework involved in the construction of “fuzzy” templates, which allow dust and emission lines to “blur” a series of empirical templates according to a series of Bayesian priors. Finally, in §4.3 we outline the framework behind importance nested sampling (INS), a robust sampling procedure that allows us to efficiently probe widely separated degeneracies.

4.1. Beyond the Grid: Perturbative Model Generation

For a set of base galaxy, emission line, and reddening templates, we wish to create a model photometry generating function P_{ptrb} that takes into account continuous evolution in as many input parameters as possible. This is especially relevant if we are interested in probing the effects of changes in the exact linear combinations of templates used (\vec{a}), emission line strengths (\vec{b}), reddening ($E(B-V)$), and redshift (z).¹⁸

¹⁸Variations on linear combinations of dust curves (\vec{c}) are unfortunately intrinsically more difficult to incorporate (see §4.1.2).

In addition to being able to handle continuous changes in parameters rather than a discrete underlying grid, we also want our function P_{ptrb} to act directly on the output photometry space \vec{F} rather than on the underlying model templates. By doing so, we will drastically decrease the time it takes to generate new photometry: since P_{trad} involves operations on large arrays containing $\gtrsim 10^{3-4}$ individual elements, similar operations on output fluxes should improve computation time by at least two to three orders of magnitude. This would make executing function calls for individual objects computationally feasible, allowing photo-z searches to move away from a pre-computed grid.

We approach this problem by breaking it into two pieces: (1) solving for the redshift evolution of an underlying set of galaxy and emission line templates without dust, and (2) solving for the effects of reddening on the subsequent set of photometry. In §4.1.1, we construct such a function that can quickly generate “baseline” (unextincted) photometry for an arbitrary linear combination of galaxy and/or emission line templates by interpolating between values generated using a fine Δz grid. In §4.1.2, we approximate the “reddening vector” $\vec{\mathcal{R}}$ for a given dust curve and underlying set of photometry as a function of $E(B-V)$ and z by fitting an exponential function to $\vec{\mathcal{R}}(E(B-V)|z)$ over a fine Δz grid and modelling the redshift evolution of each of the coefficients. Each of these points will be discussed in more detail below.

4.1.1. Generating “Baseline” Photometry

Recall that the transformed model template for an object with a given set of parameters \vec{x} was defined such that

$$\mathcal{M}(\vec{x}) \equiv \left[\sum_i a_i S_{\lambda, \text{base}, i}(\lambda) + \sum_j b_j S_{\lambda, \text{em}, j}(\lambda) \right] \times \mathcal{R}_{\text{gal}}(\lambda | \vec{c}, E(B-V)) \times \mathcal{R}_{\text{IGM}}(\lambda | z)$$

Temporarily ignoring the effects of dust (i.e. setting $\mathcal{R}_{\text{gal}} \times \mathcal{R}_{\text{IGM}} = 1$) and tracking only the j th component of the filter convolution function to our set of initial templates, we see that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}_j^{z_i}(S_{\nu, \text{gal}}) &= \frac{\int_{\lambda_{z_i}} [\sum_n a_n S_{\nu, \text{base}, n}(\nu) + \sum_m b_m S_{\nu, \text{em}, m}(\nu)] T_j(\nu) \nu^{-1} d\nu}{\int T_j(\nu) \nu^{-1} d\nu} \\ &= \frac{\int_{\lambda_{z_i}} \sum_n a_n S_{\nu, \text{base}, n}(\nu) T_j(\nu) \nu^{-1} d\nu}{\int_{\lambda_{z_i}} T_j(\nu) \nu^{-1} d\nu} + \frac{\int_{\lambda_{z_i}} \sum_m b_m S_{\nu, \text{em}, m}(\nu) T_j(\nu) \nu^{-1} d\nu}{\int_{\lambda_{z_i}} T_j(\nu) \nu^{-1} d\nu} \\ &= \sum_n a_n \frac{\int_{\lambda_{z_i}} S_{\nu, \text{base}, n}(\nu) T_j(\nu) \nu^{-1} d\nu}{\int_{\lambda_{z_i}} T_j(\nu) \nu^{-1} d\nu} + \sum_m b_m \frac{\int_{\lambda_{z_i}} S_{\nu, \text{em}, m}(\nu) T_j(\nu) \nu^{-1} d\nu}{\int_{\lambda_{z_i}} T_j(\nu) \nu^{-1} d\nu} \\ &= \sum_n a_n (F_{\text{base}, n})_j + \sum_m b_m (F_{\text{em}, m})_j, \end{aligned} \tag{42}$$

where $\int_{\lambda_{z_i}}$ again is the integral over the redshifted wavelengths $\lambda_z = (1+z)\lambda$ of the original template at a given redshift z_i .

The “baseline” (i.e. unextincted) photometry of a given galaxy template thus is the sum of the model photometry of each of its components,

$$\mathcal{F}^{z_i}(S_{\nu,\text{gal}}) = \sum_n a_n \vec{F}_{\text{base},n}(z_i) + \sum_m b_m \vec{F}_{\text{em},m}(z_i), \quad (43)$$

where $\vec{F}(z_i)$ is the photometric flux vector at a given redshift z_i . This can be written more compactly as

$$\mathcal{F}^{z_i}(S_{\nu,\text{gal}}) = \vec{F}_{\text{gal}}(z_i) = \vec{a} \cdot \mathbf{F}_{\text{base}}(z_i) + \vec{b} \cdot \mathbf{F}_{\text{em}}(z_i), \quad (44)$$

where $\mathbf{F}_{\text{base}}(z_i)$ and $\mathbf{F}_{\text{em}}(z_i)$ are the matrices formed by the set of photometric vectors created from all base galaxy and emission line templates at a given redshift z_i , where the row n and column m give the flux corresponding to a given template and filter, respectively, and \cdot is the dot product.

Given a redshift grid of N_z entries $\{z_1, \dots, z_N\}$ sampled at some resolution Δz , we could derive a corresponding set of matrices $\{\dots, \mathbf{F}_{\text{base}}(z_i), \dots\}$ and $\{\dots, \mathbf{F}_{\text{em}}(z_i), \dots\}$. This can be extended to a continuous parameterization by interpolating between each of the individual grid points using a function such as a cubic spline.¹⁹ Defining

$$\mathcal{S}_{F_{\text{base},(n,m)}}(z) \equiv \text{cspline}(\{\dots, z_i, \dots\}, \{\dots, \mathbf{F}_{\text{base},(n,m)}(z_i), \dots\}), \quad (45)$$

to be the cubic spline of the (n, m) entry of \mathbf{F}_{base} for a given grid $\{\dots, z_i, \dots\}$ with corresponding values $\{\dots, \mathbf{F}_{\text{base},(n,m)}(z_i), \dots\}$, we construct a direct function modelling the redshift evolution of the m th flux element $F_m(z)$ of the n th base (galaxy) template.

For a given template, once a spline for each component of the photometry has been constructed, we are able to declare the relevant “vector spline”,

$$\vec{\mathcal{S}}_{F_{\text{base},n}} = \{\mathcal{S}_{F_{\text{base},(n,1)}}, \mathcal{S}_{F_{\text{base},(n,2)}}, \dots, \mathcal{S}_{F_{\text{base},(n,N_{\text{filt}})}}\}. \quad (46)$$

Using the vector spline constructed for a given base template over the redshift grid, computing the corresponding $\vec{F}_{\text{base}}(z_i|n)$ at any arbitrary redshift z_i can be done without integrating over a set of filters.

Remembering that we can decompose a given \vec{F}_{gal} into a linear combination of the underlying basis galaxy and emission line photometry, we find that the corresponding photometry of an arbitrary unextincted galaxy template is

$$\vec{F}_{\text{gal}}(z|\vec{a}, \vec{b}) = \sum_n a_n \vec{\mathcal{S}}_{F_{\text{base},n}}(z) + \sum_m b_m \vec{\mathcal{S}}_{F_{\text{em},m}}(z) \quad (47)$$

$$= \vec{a} \cdot \mathcal{S}_{F_{\text{base}}}(z) + \vec{b} \cdot \mathcal{S}_{F_{\text{em}}}(z), \quad (48)$$

¹⁹For the remainder of this section, we have assumed a cubic spline has been used. However, our general findings hold true for any effective interpolation scheme provided its fixed points have been sampled to sufficient accuracy.

Fig. 23.— The redshift evolution of the normalized flux in each filter for a sample star-forming galaxy (continuum) template from Figure 6 over $z = 0-6$ at constant normalization (i.e. without luminosity distance effects) using a cubic spline with fixed points over $\Delta z = 0.01$. The error in the photometry at this Δz resolution is $\lesssim 1\%$ in most cases, indicating the general redshift evolution of the continuum flux for a given template is relatively smooth and well-approximated even at relatively coarse resolution. The shifting locations and general shape of the pseudo-Lyman (located here at the edge of the template’s wavelength coverage at $\sim 1000 \text{ \AA}$) and Balmer breaks as a function of redshift can be easily seen.

where each $\mathcal{S}_F(z)$ is now a “matrix spline” containing continuous functions of z . Using a collection of N_z matrices, we thus have replaced every element in $\mathbf{F}_{\text{base}}(z_i)$ and $\mathbf{F}_{\text{em}}(z_i)$ corresponding spline that encapsulates its evolution as a function of redshift. In other words, we have replaced a series of photometric values calculated at a *given* redshift with a series of functions that generate photometry as a *function* of redshift.

The redshift evolution of a vector spline for a given star-forming galaxy (emission line) template from Figure 6 (7) over $z = 0-6$ ($z = 0-0.5$) is shown in Figure 23 (24) for illustrative purposes. We find that our while cubic spline interpolation of the continuum is precise to $\lesssim 1\%$ for a somewhat coarse redshift grid with $\Delta z = 0.01$, for emission lines with a FWHM of $\sim 200 \text{ km/s}$, an order of magnitude finer resolution ($\Delta z \leq 0.001$) is needed to achieve the same level of accuracy and avoid fringes in regions of rapidly changing filter transmission.

Fig. 24.— Same as Figure 23, but for the emission line template from Figure 7 over $z = 0-0.5$ using a cubic spline with fixed points over $\Delta z = 0.001$. The error in the corresponding photometry at this Δz resolution is again $\lesssim 1\%$ in most cases. As expected, the resolution needed to properly resolve the redshift evolution of emission lines (with FWHM ~ 200 km/s) is an order of magnitude greater than that of the continuum, as fringes appear in regions with rapid transmission changes when $\Delta z \gtrsim 0.001$.

4.1.2. Incorporating Reddening Effects

We now wish to define a mapping from the initial (unattenuated) galaxy photometry \vec{F}_{gal} to the final (reddened) model photometry \vec{F}_{model} such that

$$\vec{F}_{\text{gal}} \xrightarrow{\mathcal{P}_{\text{ptrb}}} \vec{F}_{\text{model}},$$

where $\mathcal{P}_{\text{ptrb}}$ is again the perturbative model photometry generating function. For a given \vec{x} , we can write this mapping in terms of the “reddening vector” $\vec{\mathcal{R}}$, such that

$$\vec{F}_{\text{model}}(\vec{x}) = \vec{F}_{\text{gal}}(\vec{a}, \vec{b}, z) \times \vec{\mathcal{R}}(\vec{c}, z, E(B-V)|\vec{a}, \vec{b}), \quad (49)$$

where $\vec{\mathcal{R}}$ contains all relevant reddening effects. The goal of the rest of this section is trying to approximate this reddening vector so we can accurately “perturb” a set of initial photometry by some amount of reddening to construct the corresponding final model galaxy template.

Unfortunately, because reddening affects the overall *shape* of an underlying galaxy template in a *wavelength-dependent* way, reddening effects on the output photometry occur in a template-dependent way based on where in each broadband filter the relevant flux has fallen. As a result, there does not exist a one-to-one mapping between $\mathcal{R}(\lambda|\vec{c})$ and $\vec{\mathcal{R}}(\vec{c})$. For a given dust curve then, reddening fundamentally cannot be parameterized via a simple multiplication of the broad-band flux without regards to the underlying template.

Instead, $\vec{\mathcal{R}}$ must be calculated separately for every individual \vec{F}_{gal} and \vec{c} . However, since every \vec{F}_{gal} is equivalent to a combination of base galaxy templates and emission line templates, the final photometry of any individual model for a given \vec{x}_i with \vec{c}_i , z_i , and $E(B-V)_i$ can instead be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{F}_{\text{model}}(\vec{x}_i) &= \sum_n a_n \times \left[\vec{F}_{\text{base},n}(z_i) \times \vec{\mathcal{R}}_{\text{base},n}(z_i, E(B-V)_i | \vec{c}_i) \right] \\ &+ \sum_m b_m \times \left[\vec{F}_{\text{em},m}(z_i) \times \vec{\mathcal{R}}_{\text{em},m}(z_i, E(B-V)_i | \vec{c}_i) \right], \end{aligned} \quad (50)$$

where $\vec{\mathcal{R}}_{\text{base},n}$ and $\vec{\mathcal{R}}_{\text{em},m}$ are the corresponding reddening vectors for each base galaxy and emission line template, respectively. This can also be written as

$$\vec{F}_{\text{model}}(\vec{x}_i) = \vec{a} [\mathbf{F}_{\text{base}}(z_i) \bullet \mathcal{R}_{\text{base}}(z_i, E(B-V)_i | \vec{c}_i)] + \vec{b} [\mathbf{F}_{\text{em}}(z_i) \bullet \mathcal{R}_{\text{em}}(z_i, E(B-V)_i | \vec{c}_i)] \quad (51)$$

for additional clarity, where \bullet indicates element-wise multiplication of the corresponding matrices. We have thus transformed our original generalized 3-D function $\vec{\mathcal{R}}(\vec{c}, z, E(B-V))$ into a series of 2-D conditional functions $\vec{\mathcal{R}}(z, E(B-V) | \vec{c})$ that we are only required to solve a total of $(N_{\text{gal}} + N_{\text{em}}) \times N_{\vec{c}}$ number of times.

For a specific \vec{x}_i , the reddening vector as a function of $E(B-V)$ is by definition the ratio of the extinguished to unextinguished photometry,

$$\vec{\mathcal{R}}(E(B-V) | \vec{x}_i) = \frac{\vec{F}_{\text{model}}(E(B-V) | \vec{x}_i)}{\vec{F}_{\text{gal}}(\vec{x}_i)} = \frac{\mathcal{F}^z \left[S_{\nu, \text{base}}(\lambda | \vec{a}_i, \vec{b}_i) \times \mathcal{R}_{\text{IGM}}(\lambda | z_i) \times [R_{\text{gal}}(\lambda | \vec{c}_i)]^{E(B-V)} \right]}{\vec{a}_i \cdot \mathcal{S}_{F_{\text{base}}}(z_i) + \vec{b}_i \cdot \mathcal{S}_{F_{\text{em}}}(z_i)}, \quad (52)$$

where each component is expected to be non-linear in $E(B-V)$. If, however, $\vec{\mathcal{R}}$ or some transformed version of $\vec{\mathcal{R}}$ can be parameterized as a simple function $f(E(B-V) | \vec{r})$ of only a few parameters \vec{r} – for instance, as a low-order polynomial or exponential function – then if we can derive the evolution of the n th coefficient $r_n(z_i | \vec{x})$ on a redshift grid for each set of template combinations, we can construct a continuous interpolated function of redshift $\mathcal{S}_{r_n}(z | \vec{a}, \vec{b}, \vec{c})$ in an identical manner to the procedure above. These can then be combined to approximate the relevant reddening vector $\mathcal{R} \approx f(E(B-V) | \{\vec{\mathcal{S}}_{r_n}(z)\}_n)$.

At a fixed redshift, however, we notice that \mathcal{R}_{IGM} is *not* a function of $E(B-V)$, which introduces wavelength-dependent multiplicative offsets in the overall reddening curve. This interferes with the power-law dependence of $[\mathcal{R}_{\text{gal}}]^{E(B-V)}$, making $\vec{\mathcal{R}}$ more difficult to parameterize. Fortunately, since \mathcal{R}_{IGM} is a function of only z , we can simply opt to incorporate its contribution when constructing our base photometric splines. Defining this set of IGM-reddened base templates as

$$S_{\nu, \text{template+igm}}(\lambda | \vec{a}, \vec{b}, z) = S_{\nu, \text{template}}(\lambda | \vec{a}, \vec{b}) \times \mathcal{R}_{\text{IGM}}(\lambda | z), \quad (53)$$

we can run through the same procedure outlined above to construct the appropriate $\mathcal{S}_{F_{\text{base+igm}}}(z)$

Fig. 25.— **Top panel:** The reddening vector (circles) for a star-forming galaxy template attenuated by the Allen (1976) MW dust curve at $z = 0.95$ plotted for each filter as a function of $E(B-V)$. Our best fit exponential approximation to all computed values with $0.01 \leq E(B-V) \leq 0.5$ (large circles) are shown as solid lines. **Bottom panel:** The photometric error for the model galaxy template used in the top panel as a result of our exponential function approximation. The errors for the approximation in all cases are $< 0.5\%$, even after extrapolating out to $E(B-V)$ values much greater than used in fit.

and $\mathcal{S}_{F_{\text{em+igm}}}(z)$ matrix splines. This enables us to rewrite our reddening vector as

$$\vec{\mathcal{R}}(E(B-V)|z, \vec{x}) = \frac{\mathcal{F}^z \left[\mathcal{S}_{\nu, \text{base+igm}}(\lambda|\vec{a}, \vec{b}, z) \times [R_{\text{gal}}(\lambda|\vec{c})]^{E(B-V)} \right]}{\vec{a} \cdot \mathcal{S}_{F_{\text{base+igm}}}(z) + \vec{b} \cdot \mathcal{S}_{F_{\text{em+igm}}}(z)}, \quad (54)$$

which can now more naturally be approximated with simple analytic functions of only $E(B-V)$.

We experiment with a variety of different approximations of $\vec{\mathcal{R}}$, ultimately finding that a simple exponential function,

$$\vec{\mathcal{R}}(E(B-V)|z, \vec{x}) = \vec{r}_0 e^{-\vec{r}_1 E(B-V)} \quad (55)$$

provides the best and most robust fit to the data for a given $E(B-V)$ grid with resolution $\Delta E(B-V) \lesssim 0.01$ over the range $0.01 \leq E(B-V) \leq 2.0$ for all redshifts tested ($z = 0-10$). In other words, each component of the reddening vector can be treated as independent opacities with different normalizations and optical depths.

Since the associated component of the reddening vector $\mathcal{R}_j \rightarrow r_0$ as $E(B-V) \rightarrow 0$, however, occasional fits where $r_0 < 1$ can sometimes lead to significant errors in the computed photometry at $E(B-V) < 0.01$. To alleviate this issue without completely sacrificing possible accuracy in the extremely low dust regime, we introduce a power-law correction to the derived normalization r_0 at low $E(B-V)$ values. Assuming that $E(B-V)$ is non-negative,

$$r_0(E(B-V) < 0.01) = r_0 \times [1 + (r_0^{-5} - 1) \times |E(B-V)|]^{-\frac{1}{5}} \quad (56)$$

If $E(B-V)$ is negative, this value is simply inverted. This reduces the magnitude of the errors by a factor of $\gtrsim 2-5$.

In Figure 25, we show our approximation of $\vec{\mathcal{R}}(E(B-V))$ and its corresponding photometric errors for a sample galaxy template fitted over the range $E(B-V) = 0.01-0.5$. Over an extremely large reddening range ($E(B-V) = 0.01-2$), we find our approximation of the reddening vector often holds to better than 0.5%, allowing us to quickly and accurately reconstruct the $E(B-V)$ ranges probed by most photo-z searches.

By interpolating between $\vec{r}(z|\vec{c})$ computed on a grid of redshift values for each set of base galaxy and emission line templates, we can now calculate the set of vector splines $\{\vec{\mathcal{S}}_{r_n}(z)\}_n$ of the relevant set of n coefficients for a given model galaxy template $\mathcal{S}_{\nu, \text{model}}$. The redshift evolution of the reddening vector for a given galaxy template, dust curve, and $E(B-V)$ value over $z = 0.05-0.75$ is shown in Figure 26 for illustrative purposes.

Analogous to the baseline photometry, we can then construct a collection of $\{\vec{\mathcal{S}}_{r_n, \text{base}}(z|\vec{c})\}$ and $\{\vec{\mathcal{S}}_{r_n, \text{em}}(z|\vec{c})\}$ vector splines calculated for each underlying base galaxy and emission line templates for each dust attenuation curve \vec{c} and for each individual coefficient n . This allows us to define the “reddening vector spline” $\vec{\mathcal{S}}_{\mathcal{R}}$ of the i th base template as

$$\vec{\mathcal{S}}_{\mathcal{R}_{\text{template+igm}, i}}(z, E(B-V)|\vec{c}) \equiv \vec{\mathcal{S}}_{r_0, \text{template+igm}, i}(z|\vec{c}) \times \exp \left[-\vec{\mathcal{S}}_{r_1, \text{template+igm}, i}(z|\vec{c}) \times E(B-V) \right]. \quad (57)$$

Fig. 26.— The multiplicative reddening vector $\vec{\mathcal{R}}$ from $z = 0.05–0.75$ for the Fitzpatrick (1986) LMC dust curve with $E(B-V) = 0.1$ given the star-forming galaxy template used in Figure 23. The evolution of the vector was derived using a cubic spline sampled at $dz = 0.01$. Note that the effects of \mathcal{R}_{IGM} are not included in this figure.

This function is constructed from a combination of our exponential function approximation $f(E(B-V)|\vec{c})$ using the splined redshift evolution of the individual coefficients in each filter $\vec{\mathcal{S}}_{r_n}$ for a given \vec{c} and $S_{\nu, \text{template+igm}}$. As a result, our desired perturbative model photometry generating function is:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{P}_{\text{ptrb}}(\vec{x}|\{\mathcal{S}_F\}, \{\mathcal{S}_R\}) &\equiv \sum_i a_i \times \vec{\mathcal{S}}_{F_{\text{base+igm},i}}(z) \times \vec{\mathcal{S}}_{\mathcal{R}_{\text{base+igm},i}}(z, E(B-V)|\vec{c}) \\ &+ \sum_j b_j \times \vec{\mathcal{S}}_{F_{\text{base+igm},j}}(z) \times \vec{\mathcal{S}}_{\mathcal{R}_{\text{em+igm},i}}(z, E(B-V)|\vec{c}) \end{aligned} \quad (58)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \vec{a} \cdot [\mathcal{S}_{F_{\text{base+igm}}}(z) \bullet \mathcal{S}_{\mathcal{R}_{\text{base+igm}}}(z, E(B-V)|\vec{c})] \\ &+ \vec{b} \cdot [\mathcal{S}_{F_{\text{em+igm}}}(z) \bullet \mathcal{S}_{\mathcal{R}_{\text{em+igm}}}(z, E(B-V)|\vec{c})]. \end{aligned} \quad (59)$$

In essence, we have engineered a transformation from $\{\mathbf{F}, \mathcal{R}\}$, where each matrix element is either computed directly or selected from a pre-computed grid in parameter space, to $\{\mathcal{S}_F, \mathcal{S}_R\}$, where each element is instead a continuous function of z and $E(B-V)$. Once we construct this mapping between our discrete grid and the functions describing the continuous underlying parameter space, calculating the photometry for any given \vec{x}_i is extremely rapid and requires no integration.

In order to investigate the robustness of our approximation over a large range of redshifts and reddenings, we Monte Carlo 10,000 sets of photometry uniformly over $z = 0–10$ and $E(B-V) = 0.01–0.6$ sampling uniformly from the set of COSMOS galaxy templates and dust curves shown

Fig. 27.— Percent error in each filter (see Figure 12) as a result of the approximations utilized in creating $\mathcal{P}_{\text{ptrb}}$ -generated fluxes, as compared to their true $\mathcal{P}_{\text{trad}}$ -generated values for 10,000 sets of model photometry. Input parameters were sampled uniformly over the redshift range $z = 0-10$, $E(B-V) = 0.1-0.6$, and the set of galaxy and dust templates shown in Figures 6 and 8. While there is some general substructure present in the 2-D redshift-reddening subspace within each filter, in all cases the errors induced due to our approximations remain at the $\lesssim 1\%$ level. Emission line contributions are not shown in this figure.

in Figures 6 and 8. We then compare the percent error of each of these sets of $\mathcal{P}_{\text{ptrb}}$ -generated photometry relative to their $\mathcal{P}_{\text{trad}}$ -generated counterparts assuming a small background (to suppress signals due to deviations close to 0). The results of our trials over each of 12 filters examined in this study are shown in Figure 27. While there is some structure present in the general space for specific combinations of redshift and reddening, the associated errors due to our use of $\mathcal{P}_{\text{ptrb}}$ remain in many cases $\lesssim 0.5\%$.

To summarize, for a set of base galaxy templates, emission line templates, and dust curves, we can construct model photometry for a given set of parameters \vec{x} using the function $\mathcal{P}_{\text{trad}} = \mathcal{F}(\mathcal{M}(\vec{x}))$.

For a given redshift grid with resolution²⁰ $\Delta z \leq 0.001$, we construct a series of accurate photometric splines $\mathcal{S}_{F,\text{gal+igm}}$ and $\mathcal{S}_{F,\text{em+igm}}$ for each of the base galaxy and emission line templates (including the effects of \mathcal{R}_{IGM}), respectively.

At a given redshift, for each template above we calculate how the reddening vector $\vec{\mathcal{R}}$ for a given dust curve (i.e. \vec{c}) changes as a function of $E(B-V)$ for a given $E(B-V)$ grid with $\Delta E(B-V) \lesssim 0.01$. Using an exponential function, we are able to approximate this underlying vector to $\lesssim 1\%$ accuracy. We then construct a collection of accurate splines $\mathcal{S}_{r_n,\text{gal+igm}}(z|\vec{c})$ and $\mathcal{S}_{r_n,\text{em+igm}}(z|\vec{c})$ for the redshift evolution of each set of n coefficients for a given \vec{c} .

Using these splines, we then create the relevant set of reddening matrix splines $\mathcal{S}_{\mathcal{R}_{\text{base+igm}},n}$ and $\mathcal{S}_{\mathcal{R}_{\text{em+igm}},n}$, each of which are continuous functions in z and $E(B-V)$. Using the total collection of \mathcal{S}_F 's and $\mathcal{S}_{\mathcal{R}}$'s, we are thus able to reconstruct the baseline photometry and the relevant reddening vector for an arbitrary galaxy template (\vec{a} and \vec{b}), amount of dust attenuation (\vec{c} and $E(B-V)$), and redshift (z). This allows us to transition away from a discrete grid to instead probe how *continuous* changes in emission line strengths (\vec{b}), reddening ($E(B-V)$), and redshift (z) can affect the GOF to high accuracy.

4.2. Sampling Color Space Directly with “Fuzzy Templates”

Now that we have established a function that can generate continuous changes in photometry, we revisit the idea behind how best to use the set of galaxy, emission line, and dust templates to effectively explore color space.

Most photo- z methods use only a small collection of templates ($\lesssim 30$) to build up their relevant grid. While most of these are empirical and taken from low redshift observations, a handful are often generated from SPS models (see Figure 6). These templates are most often meant to serve as a set of baseline templates and thus do not include dust or emission line contributions.

As discussed in § 2.2, most codes take an “additive approach” by only considering non-negative $E(B-V)$ and \vec{b} values when modifying their underlying grids. As a result, in order to model many of the highly-extincted, intensely star-forming, and strongly emitting galaxies seen at higher redshifts (e.g., Masters et al. 2014; Steinhardt et al. 2014), these codes end up creating photometry using a combination of synthesized templates, large $E(B-V)$ values (applied as a uniform dust screen), coarse $E(B-V)$ sampling, and a limited number of emission line strengths often scaled based on correlations observed at low redshift (Ilbert et al. 2013; Salmon et al. 2014). This process involves a number of significant transformations to the original basis set using several assumptions that likely no longer remain strictly valid.

An alternative to this is an “archetype approach”, where instead of trying to modify some set of

²⁰Assuming the same redshift grid is used to sample both the galaxy and emission line templates.

Fig. 28.— **Top panel:** The 129 galaxy templates (normalized to $1.6 \mu\text{m}$) taken from Brown et al. (2014), colored based on their *GALEX* FUV flux (increasing from red to blue). The cubic spline fit (black) to the (normalized) transmission curve (red circles) is shown for reference. Over wavelength ranges where a galaxy was not observed, the corresponding spectrum was derived by interpolating between the observed data using *MAGPHYS* (da Cunha et al. 2008). Compared to Figure 6, the Brown et al. (2014) templates much more densely cover a significant region of color space. **Bottom panel:** Insets showing spectral features around the central wavelengths for (from left to right, top to bottom) $\text{H}\alpha+\text{N}[\text{II}]$, $\text{H}\beta$, $\text{H}\gamma$, $\text{O}[\text{II}]$, $\text{O}[\text{III}]_{4960}$, and $\text{O}[\text{III}]_{5008}$. The significant range in emission line strengths probed by the template set are clearly visible.

Fig. 29.— From top to bottom, left to right: The distribution of EWs for $H\alpha+N[II]$ (blue), $H\beta$ (green), $H\gamma$ (red), $O[II]$ (magenta), $O[III]_{5008}$ (black), and $O[III]_{4960}$ (orange). While the majority of galaxies do not display strong emission, there is an extended tail indicative of a subpopulation of strong emitters within the sample.

existing galaxy templates, we instead attempt to probe the relevant regions of color space directly. An example of such an approach has been used in the **PRISM Multi-object Survey** (PRIMUS; Coil et al. 2011; Cool et al. 2013) where, in order to derive effective redshifts, Cool et al. (2013) construct a large sample of spectral templates from the AGN and Galaxy Evolution Survey (AGES; Kochanek et al. 2012), which they then compare to each observed object over a fine redshift grid. While generally effective, this approach does not account for possible deviations away from any specific template due to varying dust extinction and/or emission line strengths, which become more significant as we move towards higher redshifts.

We wish to advocate for a hybrid of the two approaches by creating what we term “fuzzy” templates, which are constructed as follows:

1. Using a relevant collection of spectra, create a library of $N_{\text{temp,gal}}$ archetypes to get a direct probe of the range of color space occupied by galaxies.
2. For each galaxy, fit for the EWs of a set of N_{lines} relevant emission lines to create a corresponding set of N_{em} emission line templates *specific to each galaxy*.
3. Using a set of dust curves, construct $\mathcal{P}_{\text{prtb}}$ (see § 4.1).

Fig. 30.— **Top panel:** The spectrum of dwarf irregular galaxy UGCA 166 (normalized to 1.6 μm), the most extreme $\text{H}\alpha + \text{N}[\text{II}]$ emitter in our sample. The shape of the spectrum is similar to active star-forming galaxies observed at higher redshift. **Bottom panel:** The corresponding fits to (from top to bottom, left to right) $\text{H}\alpha + \text{N}[\text{II}]$, $\text{H}\beta$, $\text{H}\gamma$, $\text{O}[\text{II}]$, $\text{O}[\text{III}]_{5008}$, and $\text{O}[\text{III}]_{4960}$. Red points were included in the line, while magenta points were used to calculate the continuum (magenta line).

Fig. 31.— The 1σ (blue), 2σ (magenta), and 3σ (red) boundaries for the UGCA 166 template (thick black) from Figure 30 given normally distributed priors on $\Delta E(B-V)$ (with $\mu = 0$, $\sigma = 0.1$) and emission line strengths (with $\mu = 0$, $\sigma = 0.2 \times \max(\text{EW}, 0.005\lambda_{\text{line}})$) assuming a Calzetti et al. (2000) SB dust curve. The boundaries have been slightly jittered for additional clarity. This results in a significant expansion in UV coverage and emission line variability while retaining the overall underlying shape of the template, which should allow photo- z codes greater flexibility in fitting galaxies of a similar type.

4. Finally, superimpose a set of priors on the variation of the emission line strengths and degree of reddening, parameterized by $\Delta\vec{b}$ and $\Delta E(B-V)$, that allow for small deviations away from the base template.

This process transforms an individual galaxy’s position in color space into a multidimensional probability density centered at its original location, allowing a given template set to more accurately capture the observed variability between galaxies of similar types.

To illustrate the power of this approach, we create a set of fuzzy templates utilizing the much larger template set of 129 high-quality UV – IR spectra taken from Brown et al. (2014). The extensive multiwavelength collection of galaxy templates presented there are ideal for our purposes, probing both a large region of color space as well as galaxy types (Figure 28). In particular, the study includes a number of galaxies with extremely strong emission lines, as illustrated in Figure 29. One such example is the dwarf irregular galaxy UGCA 166 (alternately designations of I Zwicky 18, Mrk 116, and PGC 027182), which is highlighted in Figure 30.

Fig. 32.— **Left panel:** The $u - g$ versus $g - r$ distribution (in magnitudes) for the 129 Brown et al. (2014) templates, colored in order of increasing FUV emission (see Figure 28). **Right panel:** As the left panel, except now for each template we have drawn 25,000 points (plotted with the same corresponding color) from the associated set of priors in $\Delta E(B - V)$ and ΔEW . The general effect of our reddening priors can be seen by examining the semi-major axis of the ellipsoidal elongated distribution of the redder (and weakly emitting) galaxies (where the majority of the semi-minor axis of the distribution is a result of our minimum EW threshold), while the general effect of our EW priors can be seen in the much bluer (and strongly emitting) galaxies, where the two axes are more comparable.

For each galaxy, we measure the corresponding EW of $\{H\alpha + N[II], H\beta, H\gamma, O[II], O[III]_{5008}, O[III]_{4960}\}$ centered on wavelengths of $\lambda_{\text{line}} = \{6564.6, 4862.7, 4341.7, 3727.0, 5008.2, 4960.3\}$ over a corresponding $\Delta v = \pm \{2000, 1500, 1500, 1500, 1500, 1250\}$ km/s spread. We fit the continuum using a simple linear function over the region contained within $\pm 55\%$ outside of the emission line spread (see Figure 30). Our fitted values, ordered in terms of increasing FUV flux, are listed in Table 2. Combining the two O[III] lines into a single template, this leaves us with five separate emission line templates per galaxy template. We opt to use the same five dust curves as the COSMOS set.

For our priors, we set $P(\Delta E(B - V))$ to be a Gaussian prior with $\mu = 0$ and $\sigma = 0.1$ in order to probe moderate changes in reddening, and $P(\Delta \vec{b})$ to be a Gaussian prior with $\mu = 0$ and $\sigma = 0.2 \times \max(\text{EW}, 0.005\lambda_{\text{line}})$, which allows us to probe a large range in possible variability for galaxies with significant observed emission down to a minimum of several tens of angstroms. An example of the corresponding fuzzy template of UGCA 166 (Figure 30) is shown in Figure 31. We

Fig. 33.— **Left panel:** The $u - g$ versus $g - r$ distribution (in magnitudes) for UGCA 166 (blue square; see Figure 30). The effects that each dust curve (Figure 8) has on the observed colors for $E(B - V) = -0.4 - 0.4$ is overplotted as a solid line. **Right panel:** The de-reddened $u - g$ versus $g - r$ distribution, which showcasing the effect of emission line variation on the observed colors. Subsamples excluding $> 5\%$ variation in O[III] and the H α +N[II] complex are highlighted in blue and red, respectively. These demonstrate that almost all of the “fuzziness” in UGCA 166 is driven by variations in H α +N[II] (via the r band; horizontal) and O[III] (via the g band; diagonal), with lesser contributions from H β , H γ , and O[II].

note that although we have the option of applying individualized priors to each galaxy template depending on our degree of prior knowledge and uncertainty, in this case we opt to simply apply this set of priors uniformly to the entire sample of interest.

To demonstrate the “blurring” effect that fuzzy templates have on the relevant regions of color space, we illustrate the extent to which our given set of priors affect the color-color distribution of the Brown et al. (2014) templates in Figure 32. Although our choice of priors is relatively simplistic, the amount of blurring we observe relative to the original template set is quite large. This is especially true for bluer galaxies, where the emission line contributions are generally larger and thus lead to greater variation compared to many of the redder galaxies in our the sample. To further showcase how different components of our priors affect the shape of our fuzzy templates in color space, we also illustrate the effects of both individual dust curves and emission lines for the case of UGCA 166 (Figure 30) in Figure 33.

To summarize, by looking for small deviations around a set of well-chosen empirical templates that directly probe the regions of interest, fuzzy templates remain in the regime where a uniform dust screen approximation (see § 2.2) is likely to be valid, helping to ensure that any reddened photometry correctly corresponds with physically occupied regions of color space. In addition, by placing priors on independent perturbations around observed emission line strengths, fuzzy templates move away

from average scaling relations tied to multiple lines and/or other physical properties (see, e.g., Ilbert et al. 2009), allowing them to probe greater (and more physical) variability in emission line strengths. Finally, by allowing for the use of symmetrical priors, fuzzy templates naturally avoid asymmetries present in previous approaches (see §3.2.2).

4.3. Capturing Widely Separated Degeneracies using Importance Nested Sampling

As mentioned in §2.3.2 and §3.3, while MCMC-based algorithms are quite efficient at sampling high-dimensional parameter spaces, they are ineffective at characterizing highly multimodal distributions because they can only reconstruct the relative *shape* of the posterior distribution rather than the absolute values. In this section, we will give an overview of Nested Sampling (NS), a method designed to sample extremely multimodal spaces in order to recover the Bayesian evidence \mathcal{Z} – and reconstructing the posterior as a by-product – in the context of the MULTINEST algorithm (Feroz & Hobson 2008; Feroz et al. 2009, 2013). We will then outline Importance Nested Sampling (INS), a method to efficiently determine the posterior using the entire collection of trials rather than just a limited subset of them (Cameron & Pettitt 2013; Feroz et al. 2013).²¹

4.3.1. Nested Sampling

In §2.3.1, we wrote Bayes’ theroem as

$$P(\Theta|\mathbf{D}, H) = \frac{P(\mathbf{D}|\Theta, H)P(\Theta|H)}{P(\mathbf{D}|H)}.$$

For a given H , we will now define the likelihood and prior distributions to be $\mathcal{L}(\Theta) \equiv P(\mathbf{D}|\Theta)$ and $\pi(\Theta) \equiv P(\Theta)$, respectively, in the interest of clarity throughout the rest of this section. The explicit form for the Bayesian evidence $\mathcal{Z} \equiv P(\mathbf{D})$ is then

$$\mathcal{Z} = \int_{\Omega_{\Theta}} \mathcal{L}(\Theta)\pi(\Theta)d\Theta, \tag{60}$$

where Ω_{Θ} represents the domain of Θ .

NS attempts to estimate \mathcal{Z} by transforming the multidimensional evidence integral $\int_{\Omega_{\Theta}}$ into a 1D integral over an inverse survival function. We first define the survival function $X(\lambda)$ for $\mathcal{L}(\Theta)$ given $\pi(\Theta)$ as

$$X(\lambda) = \int_{\Theta:\mathcal{L}(\Theta)>\lambda} \pi(\Theta)d\Theta. \tag{61}$$

²¹See Feroz & Hobson (2008); Feroz et al. (2009, 2013) for a more extensive overview of NS and INS.

For a given λ_i , deriving the associated *prior volume* $X(\lambda_i)$ thus involves integrating over the prior for the region(s) of parameter space contained within the corresponding iso-likelihood contour $\mathcal{L}(\Theta) = \lambda$.

We can now rewrite the integral for \mathcal{Z} as the indefinite integral

$$\mathcal{Z} = \int_0^\infty X(\lambda)d\lambda, \quad (62)$$

or, in terms of the *inverse* survival function $\mathcal{L}(X)$, as the definite integral

$$\mathcal{Z} = \int_0^1 \mathcal{L}(X)dX, \quad (63)$$

where we have now transformed the likelihood from a function of the input parameters Θ to a function of the prior volume X computed over a set of iso-likelihood contours. This can then be easily approximated numerically using standard quadrature methods given a set of N values

$$0 < X_N < \dots < X_2 < X_1 < X_0 = 1$$

and their associated \mathcal{L}_N values using

$$Z \approx \hat{Z} \equiv \sum_{i=1}^N \mathcal{L}_i w_i, \quad (64)$$

where the weights w_i are given by $w_i = \frac{1}{2}(X_{i-1} - X_{i+1})$ (i.e. the trapezoid rule). As $\mathcal{L}(X)$ is typically unknown, numerical methods must be employed to estimate the prior volume X_i associated with a given likelihood contour $\mathcal{L}(X_i)$ in order to perform this integration.

The default NS algorithm is as follows. First, N_{live} ‘live’ points are drawn from the prior $\pi(\Theta)$ and the initial prior volume X_0 is set to unity. At each subsequent iteration i , the point with the lowest \mathcal{L}_i is removed from the set and replaced with another drawn from the prior under the constraint $\mathcal{L}_{i+1} > \mathcal{L}_i$. At each iteration i , the prior volume is thus a random variable such that

$$X_i = t_i X_{i-1}, \quad (65)$$

where

$$P(t_i) = N_{\text{live}} t_i^{N_{\text{live}}-1}. \quad (66)$$

As this sampling process is repeated, the live particles move through *nested* shells of constrained likelihood as the prior volume is steadily reduced, finally terminating after reaching a specific tolerance threshold.

The geometrical exploration of the prior volume can be understood through the behavior of $\log t$, of which the expectation value and variance are

$$\langle \log t \rangle = -1/N_{\text{live}}, \quad (67)$$

$$\sigma^2(\log t) = 1/N_{\text{live}}. \quad (68)$$

Since each draw of $\log t_i$ is independent, after i iterations the prior volume will shrink down as $\log X_i \approx -(i \pm \sqrt{i})/N_{\text{live}}$. As a result,

$$X_i \approx \exp(-i/N_{\text{live}}) \quad (69)$$

serves as a reasonable approximation of the prior volume at a given iteration.

An estimate of the posterior can then be obtained using the final set of live points and the full sequence of live points that were discarded during the NS process. After assigning each point the relevant *importance weight*,

$$p_i = \frac{\mathcal{L}_i w_i}{\sum_j \mathcal{L}_j w_j} = \frac{\mathcal{L}_i w_i}{\hat{Z}}, \quad (70)$$

we can then compute key sample-based quantities from our data such as 1D marginalized posterior distributions.²²

In order to efficiently draw unbiased samples efficiently from the likelihood-constrained prior, **MULTINEST** utilizes an ellipsoidal decomposition scheme. At each iteration i , the full set of N_{live} points is decomposed to lie within a set of (possibly overlapping) ellipsoids that can be evolved separately, allowing the algorithm to probe widely separated minima. The desired replacement $\mathcal{L}_{i+1} > \mathcal{L}_i$ is then selected from a particular ellipse, where at a given iteration i the probability that a particular ellipsoid l with volume V_l is chosen out of a set of L ellipsoids is

$$p_l = V_l/V_{\text{tot}}, \quad (71)$$

where $V_{\text{tot}} = \sum_{l=1}^L V_l$ is the total volume of all ellipsoids.²³ After an ellipsoid has been chosen, samples are drawn uniformly within it until a point satisfies $\mathcal{L}_{i+1} > \mathcal{L}_i$ if found. This point is then accepted with probability

$$p_{\text{acc}} = 1/q, \quad (72)$$

where q is the number of ellipsoids the new point lies in. If the point is rejected, the process is repeated with a new random choice of ellipsoid.

As this ellipsoidal decomposition scheme is crucial to the effectiveness of NS over competing methods, it is described in more detail below.

²²Note that unlike the grid-based case (but similar to the MCMC case), these distributions now are sampled arbitrarily rather than at fixed resolution. However, *unlike* the MCMC case, where we attempt to sample at a rate proportional to the probability and thus only need to track the positions of accepted trials, using NS we are sampling much more sparsely, and thus need to utilize appropriate weights in order to derive relevant posterior quantities (similar to the grid-based case).

²³It is important to note that this is not the total volume contained in the *union* of all ellipsoids, but just in the collection of ellipsoids themselves (see § 4.3.3).

4.3.2. Ellipsoidal Decomposition in *MULTINEST*

At a given iteration i , for a set $S = \{\vec{u}_1, \vec{u}_2, \dots, \vec{u}_{N_{\text{live}}}\}$ of N_{live} live points uniformly sampled from a given volume $V(S) = X_i = \exp(-i/N_{\text{live}})$ of dimension D , we can partition the set into $K \geq 1$ clusters $\{S_{k=1}, \dots, S_{k=K}\}$ (where $\cup_{k=1}^K S_k = S$) containing n_k corresponding live points by means of, e.g., a k -means clustering algorithm. A reasonably accurate and computationally efficient approach to approximating the minimum volume of the bounding ellipsoid E_k of the subset S_k is

$$E_k = \{\vec{u} \in \mathbb{R}^D | d(\vec{u}, S_k) \leq 1\}, \quad (73)$$

where

$$d(\vec{u}, S_k) = (\vec{u} - \vec{\mu}_k)^T (f_k \Sigma_k)^{-1} (\vec{u} - \vec{\mu}_k) \quad (74)$$

is the normalized distance from \vec{u} to the centroid $\vec{\mu}_k = \frac{1}{n_k} \sum_{j=1}^{n_k} u_j$ of the ellipsoid,

$$\Sigma_k = \frac{1}{n_k} \sum_{j=1}^{n_k} (\vec{u}_j - \vec{\mu}_k)(\vec{u}_j - \vec{\mu}_k)^T \quad (75)$$

is the computed covariance matrix of S_k around $\vec{\mu}_k$, and f_k is the enlargement factor chosen to ensure that E_k is a bounding ellipsoid such that

$$V(E_k) = \max [V(E_k), V(S_k)], \quad (76)$$

where

$$V(E_k) \propto \sqrt{\det(f_k \Sigma_k)} \quad (77)$$

is the volume of E_k and

$$V(S_k) = \frac{n_k V(S)}{N_{\text{live}}} \quad (78)$$

is the volume of a given subset $V(S_k)$.

We now define the fractional volume covered by these series of ellipsoids as

$$F(S) \equiv \frac{1}{V(S)} \sum_{k=1}^K V(E_k). \quad (79)$$

For a given set of K partitions, minimizing $F(S)$ with the constraint $F(S) \geq 1$ (i.e. $\sum_k V(E_k) \geq V(S)$) yields an optimal decomposition of the original sampled region into K ellipsoids that still effectively encloses the set. The main challenges then are determining an effective method to minimize this function as well as the minimum number of ellipsoids K_{min} that can effectively bound the set. We tackle each of these issues in turn.

For uniformly distributed points, reassigning a live point with position \vec{u} from a subset S_k to an alternate subset $S_{k'}$ leads to variation in $F(S)$ of the form (Lu et al. 2007)

$$\Delta F(S)_{k,k'} \propto \left[\frac{V(E_{k'})d(\vec{u}, S_{k'})}{V(S_{k'})} - \frac{V(E_k)d(\vec{u}, S_k)}{V(S_k)} \right]. \quad (80)$$

Defining

$$h_k(\vec{u}) \equiv \frac{V(E_k)d(\vec{u}, S_k)}{V(S_k)}, \quad (81)$$

we see that strictly minimizing $F(S)$ (i.e. setting $\Delta F(S) < 0$) leads to the condition that we (re)assign $u \in S_k$ to $S_{k'}$ (where $k \neq k'$) when

$$h_{k'}(\vec{u}) < h_k(\vec{u}). \quad (82)$$

As a result, given two ellipses E_1 and E_2 constructed by partitioning S into S_1 and S_2 , to minimize $F(S)$ we simply assign all points $\{\vec{u}_1, \dots, \vec{u}_{N_{\text{live}}}\}$ to the corresponding S_k such that $h_k(\vec{u}) = \min[h_1(\vec{u}), h_2(\vec{u})]$. This process can be done iteratively until an optimal partition is found.

Finally, for a given set of points in S , this scheme can be applied recursively to continually sort points into more refined optimal subsets until some desired quality threshold is achieved, thus allowing us to achieve the minimum number of optimal partitions/ellipsoids K_{min} necessary to describe a given distribution of live points. In MULTINEST, this procedure²⁴ continues as long as $V(E_1) + V(E_2) < V(E_{\text{rec}})$ or $V(E) > 2V(S_{\text{rec}})$, where S_{rec} and E_{rec} are the recursive subset and the bounding ellipsoid, respectively, to which the algorithm is currently being applied. This guarantees that the partitioning continues until the volume enclosed by the new bounding ellipsoids exceeds that of the original bounding ellipsoid (i.e. is more inefficient) or a given quality threshold is reached (in this case $2V(S_{\text{rec}})$).

The minimization procedure described above can be computationally expensive (especially as D becomes large) given the number of eigenvector and eigenvalue evaluations necessary to compute each of the $V(E_k)$'s. In order to minimize the number of decompositions, once a series of ellipsoids are computed, MULTINEST attempts to simply scale them in future iterations such that

$$V(E_k) = \max[V(E_k), X_{i+1}n_k/N_{\text{live}}], \quad (83)$$

where X_{i+1} is the remaining prior volume in the next nested sampling iteration and n_k is the number of points in S_k at the end of the current (i th) iteration. This process is done until a quality threshold $F(S) \leq h$ fails to be satisfied, where typically $h = 1.1$.

4.3.3. Importance Nested Sampling

As mentioned above, “vanilla” NS estimation of both the Bayesian evidence \mathcal{Z} and posterior quantities only make use of the final and discarded set of live points. As the sampling efficiency is often (intentionally) $< 50\%$, in most cases this results in a majority of trials being discarded, much like the case with MCMC-based algorithms such as `emcee` and our implementation of `BAD-Z`.

²⁴For a more detailed overview, see Feroz et al. (2009).

INS sampling, a method of utilizing *all* trials taken during NS, was proposed by Cameron & Pettitt (2013) and implemented in MULTINEST by Feroz et al. (2013). The general implementation (which we will use) is summarized below.

We first define the *pseudo-importance sampling density* $g(\Theta)$ as

$$g(\Theta) = \frac{1}{N_{\text{tot}}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{iter}}} \frac{n_i \epsilon_i(\Theta)}{V_{\text{tot},\cup,i}}, \quad (84)$$

where N_{iter} is the total number of iterations²⁵ (i.e. ellipsoidal decompositions) performed by MULTINEST, n_i is the number of points collected at the i th iteration (i.e. the number of trials computed during each decomposition), $N_{\text{tot}} = \sum_i^{N_{\text{iter}}} n_i$ is the total number of trials, $V_{\text{tot},\cup,i}$ is the total volume enclosed in the *union* of ellipsoids at the i th iteration (in contrast to the V_{tot} defined previously), and $\epsilon_i(\Theta)$ is an indicator function that returns 1 when Θ lies within the i th ellipsoidal decomposition and 0 otherwise.²⁶

In other words, for a given set of parameters Θ , we compute $g(\Theta)$ by summing over a set of volume-normalized (by $V_{\text{tot},\cup,i}$) and sampling-normalized (by N_{tot}) weights at each iteration i such that

$$w_{\text{INS},i} \equiv \frac{1}{N_{\text{tot}}} \frac{n_i}{V_{\text{tot},\cup,i}}. \quad (85)$$

These are only included if Θ is contained within the elliptical decomposition of the prior volume X_i at a given iteration. As points that occupy regions of higher likelihood will be contained within elliptical decompositions for a greater number of iterations than those that occupy regions of lower likelihood, $g(\Theta)$ serves a similar function to the original importance weight $p_i = \mathcal{L}_i w_i / \hat{Z}$ defined in § 4.3.1.

As the total volume at a given iteration i enclosed in the union of all ellipsoids $V_{\text{tot},\cup,i}$ is not equivalent to the total volume enclosed by all ellipsoids $V_{\text{tot},i} = \sum_{l=1}^L V_l$, we must resort to estimating $V_{\text{tot},\cup,i}$ numerically. Using an MC method, this can be done in a straightforward manner. For each ellipsoidal decomposition, we draw a point Θ'_m uniformly from a given ellipsoid selected with probability $p = V_{l,i}/V_{\text{tot},i}$ and compute the number of ellipsoidals it lies in (q_m). After repeating this process M times, the volume contained in the union of ellipsoids can be approximated by

$$V_{\text{tot},\cup,i} \approx \hat{V}_{\text{tot},\cup,i} = \frac{M}{\sum_{m=1}^M q_m} \sum_{l=1}^L V_l. \quad (86)$$

As this MC procedure does not require any evaluations of the likelihood function, it is not computationally demanding and can be computed relatively quickly.

²⁵While MULTINEST does not explicitly compute new decompositions at every iteration, it still implicitly creates new ones by evolving the previous decomposition, as discussed in § 4.3.2.

²⁶As $g(\Theta)$ is only defined *a posteriori* to our sampling from it, all $\Theta \sim \epsilon_{j>i}(\Theta)$ are to some degree (hopefully negligible) dependent on all previous draws $\Theta \sim \epsilon_{j\leq i}(\Theta)$. See Feroz et al. (2013) for further discussion on this issue.

As mentioned in §4.3.1, to account for volume overlap between ellipsoids MULTINEST only *accepts* a new valid ($\mathcal{L}_{i+1} > \mathcal{L}_i$) trial point Θ_{i+1} with a probability of $1/q_{i+1}$. All the information included in the rejected trials would thus not be included using the framework defined above. Since these may constitute a significant portion of the actual number of trials, we modify our pseudo-importance sampling density in order to include them by dividing it into three components such that

$$g(\Theta) = g_1(\Theta) + g_2(\Theta) + g_3(\Theta), \quad (87)$$

where, assuming that Θ was drawn at a given iteration i , $g_1(\Theta)$, $g_2(\Theta)$, and $g_3(\Theta)$ represent the contributions from the i th iteration, all $j < i$ prior iterations, and all $j > i$ subsequent iterations, respectively. This leads to the following forms for $g_1(\Theta)$, $g_2(\Theta)$, and $g_3(\Theta)$:

$$g_1(\Theta) = \frac{1}{N_{\text{tot}}} \frac{qn_i}{V_{\text{tot},\cup,i}}, \quad (88)$$

$$g_2(\Theta) = \frac{1}{N_{\text{tot}}} \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} \frac{n_j}{V_{\text{tot},\cup,j}}, \quad (89)$$

$$g_3(\Theta) = \frac{1}{N_{\text{tot}}} \sum_{j=i+1}^{N_{\text{iter}}} \frac{n_j \epsilon_j(\Theta)}{V_{\text{tot},\cup,j}}. \quad (90)$$

Using the psueudo-importance sampling density, the Bayesian evidence can now be estimated using the total number of trials (accepted or rejected) as

$$\hat{\mathcal{Z}}_{\text{INS}} = \frac{1}{N_{\text{tot}}} \sum_{k=1}^{N_{\text{tot}}} \frac{\mathcal{L}(\Theta_k)\pi(\Theta_k)}{g(\Theta_k)}, \quad (91)$$

for all Θ_k , with a (slightly biased) error of

$$\hat{\sigma}^2(\hat{\mathcal{Z}}_{\text{INS}}) = \frac{1}{N_{\text{tot}}(N_{\text{tot}} - 1)} \sum_{k=1}^{N_{\text{tot}}} \left[\frac{\mathcal{L}(\Theta_k)\pi(\Theta_k)}{g(\Theta_k)} - \hat{\mathcal{Z}}_{\text{INS}} \right]^2. \quad (92)$$

In addition to \mathcal{Z} , each Θ_k can also be assigned the following estimate of its posterior probability density $P_{\text{INS}}(\Theta_k|\mathbf{D})$ via

$$P_{\text{INS}}(\Theta_k|\mathbf{D}) = \frac{\mathcal{L}(\Theta_k)\pi(\Theta_k)}{N_{\text{tot}}g(\Theta_k)}. \quad (93)$$

Using INS, we thus are able to use the entirety of trials computed using MULTINEST to probe our marginalized probability distributions of interest. It thus represents an effective and efficient way to sampled widely separated regions of parameter space in order to better characterize the multimodal likelihoods that show up during photo-z search process without being forced to resort to a grid-based approach.

5. Conclusion

Photometric redshifts (photo-z’s) represent an integral part of modern extragalactic science, but their current inadequacy in the face of looming future “big data”-oriented surveys – in both accuracy and computational efficiency – is concerning. This thesis represents a concerted effort to improve photo-z codes through a combined computationally and statistically-oriented approach from both perspectives. Our main results are as follows:

1. Using a pre-generated grid of ~ 2 million elements based on (Ilbert et al. 2009) with a redshift resolution of $\Delta z = 0.005$, we create the first ever maps of the associated photo-z likelihood surface.
2. Based on these maps, we find that the surface is significantly “bumpy”, with a large number of minima that often occupy a much larger area (in terms of the overall gradient) than the global best-fit value. In addition, we observe small contributions due to asymmetries inherent in the “additive” approach of generating model photometry.
3. Building on these results, we are able design a specific algorithm (BAD-Z) optimized to explore pre-generated model photometry grids during photo-z searches through the combination of a swarm intelligence-based MCMC implementation (via `emcee`; Foreman-Mackey et al. 2013) with a smoothing metaheuristic (via simulated annealing).
4. After creating a mock catalog from $\sim 380,000$ COSMOS (Scoville et al. 2007) galaxies for a set of 12 filters spanning the UV to the IR, we test the performance of BAD-Z over a wide wavelength and redshift range. Compared to a grid-based counterpart (GRPEZ), we find BAD-Z is at least 40–50 times more computationally efficient, retains similar levels of accuracy, and performs robustly over the entire redshift range probed.
5. Taking advantage of a set of interpolations and approximations, we develop a “perturbative” method (via $\mathcal{P}_{\text{ptrb}}$) for generating photometry for a continuous range of inputs in emission line strengths, redshift, and reddening (and linear combinations of galaxy templates). We verify that our method is robust across a wide range of input parameters and accurate to $\lesssim 0.5\text{--}1\%$ in almost all cases.
6. From these results, we develop a framework around the implementation of “fuzzy” templates in photo-z fitting routines that allows for the use of a (large) empirical template library of “archetypes” that simultaneously incorporates intrinsic uncertainties in individual galaxy templates (in both reddening and emission line strengths) via a set of appropriately chosen Bayesian priors. We then demonstrate their utility in future photo-z codes using data from Brown et al. (2014).
7. Finally, we review the motivation, implementation, and usefulness of Importance Nested Sampling (INS) via MULTINEST (Feroz & Hobson 2008; Feroz et al. 2009, 2013) in capturing widely-

separated degeneracies that MCMC-based sampling routines often miss. This is particularly relevant in improving the precision and robustness of future photo- z algorithms.

While many of these results are extremely promising, they are merely the first steps towards a rigorous attempt to improve photo- z 's. Most directly, combining our newly established $\mathcal{P}_{\text{ptrb}}$ -driven framework for incorporating fuzzy templates along with the use of INS has yet to be completed and tested, both using mock catalogs – such as the one used in this work – as well as real data – such as the deep, high-quality, multi-wavelength data and associated spectra from the ongoing SPLASH (SPitzer Large Area Survey with HYper-Suprime Cam; Capak et al. 2012; Steinhardt et al. 2014) survey. Such a combination would likely be extremely useful in moving towards a combined framework for dealing with the computational and modelling issues associated with computing photo- z 's.

In addition, almost all photo- z codes – including the ones in this work – utilize exclusively color information when deriving their associated $P(z)$'s. This, however, ignores valuable and potentially important spatial information including positional uncertainties, clustering information, morphology, and observed size, all of which might provide information that might either improve accuracy or help distinguish the dominant mode(s) of a multimodal redshift PDF. In particular, incorporating clustering information through, e.g., the methods outlined in Ménard et al. (2013) would be a useful next step towards exhausting all available information contained in photometric surveys.

Furthermore, while this work has focused almost exclusively on model (i.e. template)-fitting approaches to deriving photo- z 's, it has ignored a wide range of machine learning techniques that are almost certainly useful in improving upon current photo- z methodologies. In particular, (un)supervised machine learning approaches such as Self-Organizing Maps (SOMs; Carrasco Kind & Brunner 2014b; Daniel Masters et al. 2015, in prep.) or Random Forests (Carrasco Kind & Brunner 2014a) offer the opportunity to move beyond simple inverse mapping approaches and instead incorporating prior knowledge about a given dataset in increasingly sophisticated ways. For instance, a SOM could be used to create a data-driven set of color-based priors utilizing clustering-based redshifts informed by the general distribution of the population of galaxies in question and/or provide a much more efficient starting location for likelihood searches, while Random Forests might significantly improve the process of incorporating previous spectroscopic redshift information into photo- z estimation. Combining model-fitting approaches with machine learning methods thus contains a lot of unrealized potential.

Moreover, during the past two decades, advances in SED fitting has led to a deeper understanding of the relationships between different physical parameters such as stellar mass, SFRs/SFHs, dust attenuation, and rest-frame colors among star-forming galaxies as a function of redshift (Williams et al. 2009; Garn & Best 2010; Leitner 2012; Whitaker et al. 2012; Bouwens et al. 2012; Reddy et al. 2012; Arnouts et al. 2013; Speagle et al. 2014; Capak et al. 2015), the evolving relationship between star-forming galaxies and quiescents (Brammer et al. 2011; Behroozi et al. 2013), the evolution of their corresponding luminosity and mass functions over a variety of redshifts (Ilbert et al. 2013;

Moustakas et al. 2013; Tomczak et al. 2014), and constraints on the redshift evolution of the cosmic star formation rate density (Hopkins & Beacom 2006; Behroozi et al. 2013). However, since most photo-z codes utilize empirical templates rather than those generated from SPS models, almost none of this information is utilized during most photo-z searches. Trying to bridge the gap in order to utilize large set of physical constraints available could open the door to utilizing photo-z’s more broadly as an expanded set of SED fitting techniques.

Finally, while this thesis has focused on many of the more computationally-oriented avenues towards improving photometric redshifts, a major unresolved issue in current photo-z searches is the dual set of model uncertainties that arise due to the use of local galaxy templates to probe galaxies at much higher redshifts and the limited range of dust templates often used during the fitting process. With regards to the first issue of template bias and/or mismatch, one additional avenue to pursue in the future would be constructing an improved set of templates either using some combination of individual and/or stacked spectra taken over a variety of redshifts, or possibly creating a set of photometrically-derived templates from the enormous amount of multi-band photometry available in most modern surveys, or a combination of the two. With regards to the issue of dust curve limitations, especially concerning common systematic features such as the 2175 Å bump (see Appendix A), the framework outlined during the construction of $\mathcal{P}_{\text{prtb}}$ offers the opportunity of incorporating these approaches through a series of approximated transformations of the parameterization of the reddening vector presented in this work, possibly lending our approach an additional level of flexibility during the fitting process. Both of these opportunities would be worthwhile to explore further.

Ultimately, while this thesis introduces many advances important to improving the quality and performance of existing and future photo-z codes, there remains ample opportunities for further investigation. Many of the big data-oriented approaches presented here, however, have applications far outside the realm of photo-z’s, and illustrate the power of thinking about large datasets – and the methods used to probe them – in different ways.

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Fig. 34.— Variation in the overall shape of the dust curve for changes in the FUV curvature c_{FUV} relative to a reference dust curve (Fitzpatrick 1986; dashed black line and black circles).

A. An Expanded Parameterization of Extragalactic Dust Curves

Creating a continuous parameterization of extragalactic dust that can fit the shape and variation of observed reddening laws from the FUV to the FIR is a challenging task because of the large amount of large amount of observed variation present in both MW and extragalactic reddening curves (Fitzpatrick & Massa 2007; Draine & Li 2007). In order to best capture the variation present in MW extinction curves, for instance, Fitzpatrick & Massa (2007) utilize an empirical 12-parameter fit that divides up the curve into two separate portions (UV and optical-IR). As theirs is among the most thorough in the literature, we outline their fitting methodology here to showcase the detail needed to capture the level of variation present in observed dust curves.

In the UV ($\lambda < 2700 \text{ \AA}$), Fitzpatrick & Massa (2007) parameterize their MW dust curves as

$$k_{\text{UV}}(\lambda - V) = \begin{cases} c_1 + c_2x + c_b D(x, x_0, \gamma), & x \leq c_5, \\ c_1 + c_2x + c_b D(x, x_0, \gamma) + c_{\text{FUV}}(x - c_5)^2, & x > c_5, \end{cases} \quad (\text{A1})$$

where $x \equiv \lambda^{-1}$ in units of inverse microns (μm), c_{FUV} is the FUV curvature, and $D(x, x_0, \gamma)$ is the Drude function,

$$D(x, x_0, \gamma) = \frac{x^2}{(x^2 - x_0^2)^2 + x^2 \gamma^2}, \quad (\text{A2})$$

with x_0 and γ the central position and width of the feature, respectively. This ‘‘bump’’ (most often

Fig. 35.— Variation in the overall shape of the dust curve for changes in the UV attenuation slope β_{UV} from $1500 \text{ \AA} - 2800 \text{ \AA}$ relative to a reference dust curve (Allen 1976; dashed black line and black circles). The UV boundary is indicated by a cyan line.

located around $\sim 2175 \text{ \AA}$) is a common observed feature among both Galactic (Fitzpatrick & Massa 2007) and extragalactic (Kriek & Conroy 2013; Scoville et al. 2014) dust curves (see also Figure 8) and has been observed to vary significantly among both sources (Fitzpatrick & Massa 2007; Kriek & Conroy 2013).

In the optical-IR regime, curves are instead fit with a cubic spline using a set of variable anchor points in the UV (U_1, U_2), optical (O_1, O_2, O_3), and IR (I_1, I_2, I_3, I_4, I_5). The two UV points are the values at 2600 and 2700 \AA derived from the k_{UV} formula above, and are used to ensure that the UV and optical portions of the extinction curve join together smoothly. The three optical points (at $3300, 4000,$ and 5530 \AA , respectively) are free parameters in the fit. Finally, the five IR points (at $0.0, 0.25, 0.50, 0.75,$ and $1.0 \mu\text{m}^{-1}$, respectively) are functions of two parameters, k_{IR} and $R(V)$,²⁷ such that

$$I_n \equiv k(\lambda_n - V) = k_{IR} \lambda_n^{-1.84} - R(V). \quad (\text{A3})$$

Note that this process of splining through anchor points is only used because Fitzpatrick & Massa (2007) do not find an acceptable analytical expression for the shape of the curve over this range.

Excluding the LMC and SMC, the most popular (and one of the only available) extragalactic

²⁷Note that this is a different quantity than the reddening function $R(\lambda)$ defined in § 2.2.

Fig. 36.— Variation in the overall shape of the dust curve for changes in the optical attenuation slope β_{opt} from $3000 \text{ \AA} - 3500 \text{ \AA}$ relative to a reference dust curve (Seaton 1979; dashed black line and black circles). The UV and optical boundaries are indicated by cyan and red lines, respectively.

dust curves comes from Calzetti et al. (2000). Using a sample of nearby SB galaxies, they find

$$k(\lambda) = \begin{cases} 2.659(-1.857 + 1.040x) + R(V), & 0.63 \leq \lambda \leq 2.20 \mu\text{m}, \\ 2.659(-2.156 + 1.509x - 0.198x^2 + 0.011x^3) + R(V), & 0.12 \leq \lambda \leq 0.63 \mu\text{m}. \end{cases} \quad (\text{A4})$$

Although the Calzetti et al. (2000) dust curve has a different shape than those of Fitzpatrick & Massa (2007), there is a common element in the way that the UV and IR portions appear to be decoupled.

Together, both of these empirical formalisms grant some insight into the underlying physics behind dust formation. However, either parameterization does not involve explicit dependencies on observable quantities such as the k_{UV} slope. In addition, they both involve a decently large number of fitted parameters — 11 in the former case and 6 in the latter (excluding zero-point $R(V)$ dependences).

Given the limited number of dust parameterizations used in photo-z codes, a parameterization that depends on only a few observable quantities is highly desirable. Furthermore, such a parameterization could be used to extend dust curves currently limited exclusively to the UV (e.g., Seaton 1979; Fitzpatrick 1986) to longer wavelengths in a more holistic way.

One of the biggest challenges to fitting dust curves is the overall normalization of $k(\lambda)$, often

Fig. 37.— Variation in the overall shape of the dust curve for changes in the NIR attenuation slope β_{NIR} from $7000 \text{ \AA} - 8000 \text{ \AA}$ relative to a reference dust curve (Prevot et al. 1984; dashed black line and black circles). The UV and optical boundaries are indicated by cyan and red lines, respectively.

parameterized in terms of $R(V)$. As $\mathcal{R}(\lambda) \propto 10^{-0.4 \times k(\lambda)}$, an arbitrary offset C such that $k'(V) = k(V) + C = R(V)$ leads to scaled version of the original reddening function $\mathcal{R}'(\lambda) = 10^{-0.4C} \times \mathcal{R}(\lambda)$. As scaling factors are separable from the filter convolution process (see § 2.2), $\vec{F}'_{\text{model}} = 10^{-0.4C} \vec{F}_{\text{model}}$. Since an arbitrary scaling factor s is then applied to all model fluxes during the fitting process, this extra multiplicative factor does not affect the χ^2 fitting process in any way.

As a result, we normalize all curves in our analysis such that $k(\lambda = 2.5 \mu\text{m}) = 0$, since at such red wavelengths little dust extinction is present. In addition, we also impose the physical condition $k(\lambda > 2.5 \mu\text{m}) = 0$, which helps retain physicality while also allowing the fitting procedure more flexibility to match the NIR portion of the curve.

After experimenting with a variety of different fitting methodologies, we find that splitting the curves into UV ($< 2850 \text{ \AA}$), optical ($2850 - 6800 \text{ \AA}$), and IR ($> 6800 \text{ \AA}$) components gives the most robust fits for a variety of possible parameterizations. We define three observable quantities corresponding to each portion of the dust curve,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \beta_{\text{UV}} &= [k(2800 \text{ \AA}) - k(1500 \text{ \AA})] / 10^3 \text{ \AA}, \\
 \beta_{\text{opt}} &= [k(3500 \text{ \AA}) - k(3000 \text{ \AA})] / 10^3 \text{ \AA}, \\
 \beta_{\text{NIR}} &= [k(8000 \text{ \AA}) - k(7000 \text{ \AA})] / 10^4 \text{ \AA}.
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{A5}$$

Fig. 38.— Variation in the overall shape of the dust curve for changes in the strength of the 2175 Å bump c_b relative to a reference dust curve (Seaton 1979; dashed black line and black circles).

Each of these linear extinction gradients describes the rough shape of the dust curve over the relevant wavelength range.

After investigating several possibilities, we find that a 5-parameter fit (to account for the general shape [3], FUV curvature [1], and the 2175 Å feature [1]) gives the most robust results for the five extinction curves considered in this study. We include six different dust curves in our main analysis: the five used in Ilbert et al. (2009) plus an additional curve taken from early results derived from a collection of high- z galaxies (Scoville et al. 2014) normalized to Prevot et al. (1984).²⁸

²⁸Because the shape of the (Scoville et al. 2014) dust curve depends significantly on the chosen normalization, this process dramatically affects the fitted parameters. As shown in Scoville et al. (2014), the curve should actually be normalized to the Calzetti et al. (2000) curve where it can be easily seen to be of the same form but with an addition feature around 2175 Å. However, as the analysis presented in this section does not change significantly with the curve removed, we opt to keep it in for completeness.

Fig. 39.— The set of 6 reddening laws used in this work with their best-fit parameterized functions overplotted, vertically offset by a small amount for additional clarity.

The UV portion of our parameterization is broken up into two parts: a general UV term $k_{UV}(\lambda)$ term and a FUV curvature “correction” $k_{FUV}(\lambda)$. Using a similar formalism to Fitzpatrick (2004), we model the UV portion as a cubic polynomial in x ,

$$k_{UV}(\lambda) = u_1x + u_2x^2 + u_3x^3, \quad \lambda < 2850 \text{ \AA}, \quad (\text{A6})$$

and the FUV curvature as a shifted quadratic term that only applies at higher wavelengths,

$$k_{FUV}(\lambda|c_{FUV}) = c_{FUV} \times [0.5392(x - 5.9)^2 + 0.05644(x - 5.9)^3], \quad x > 5.9, \quad (\text{A7})$$

which accounts for the often steeper FUV rise. We find that the coefficients u_1 , u_2 , and u_3 are well fit by quadratic functions in β_{UV} , such that

$$\begin{aligned} u_1(\beta_{UV}) &= -0.0627\beta_{UV}^2 - 1.3160\beta_{UV} + 1.4159, \\ u_2(\beta_{UV}) &= +0.0158\beta_{UV}^2 + 0.2202\beta_{UV} - 0.1977, \\ u_3(\beta_{UV}) &= -0.0012\beta_{UV}^2 - 0.0167\beta_{UV} + 0.0082. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A8})$$

The effects each of these components have on the shape of the dust curve are shown in Figures 34 and 35.

As mentioned earlier, two of the available dust curves were only observed in the UV. Traditionally, these are extended to the optical and IR by simply adding on points from the similar-looking

Fig. 40.— Absolute errors from our parameterization relative to the data/previous parameterization(s) for each of the dust curves presented in Figure 39. Errors on the fit are generally small throughout the wavelength range of interest, peaking around ~ 0.2 mag in the FUV.

Allen (1976) Milky Way curve after accounting for offsets in $R(V)$. However, this introduces slight breaks and discontinuities since each curve has slightly different shapes in the UV and different extinction gradients as they approach the optical regime.

Using our fits to the UV portions of each curve, we stitch these curves together more smoothly. Using the extinction gradient $d\beta/d\lambda$ for each curve per 100 \AA , we connect the curves at the closest λ_β in the extended regime where the extinction gradients of each curve and the underlying Allen (1976) curve differ by $< 5\%$. These extended curves are then used throughout the rest of the fitting process.

The optical portion of the curve is well parameterized by a quadratic polynomial in $\lambda_{\text{opt}} = (\lambda - 0.2850) \mu\text{m}$ (as opposed to x). Our best fit (Figure 36) is

$$k_{\text{opt}}(\lambda) = o_1 \lambda_{\text{opt}} + o_2 \lambda_{\text{opt}}^2 + R_{\text{opt}}, \quad 2850 \text{ \AA} \leq \lambda < 6800 \text{ \AA}, \quad (\text{A9})$$

where $R_{\text{opt}} = k_{\text{UV}}(x = 0.2850^{-1} \mu\text{m}^{-1} | \beta_{\text{UV}})$ is a simple normalization factor used to ensure continuity. The coefficients are well fit by linear functions in β_{opt} , such that

$$\begin{aligned} o_1 &= +14.9716\beta_{\text{opt}} + 7.6787 \\ o_2 &= -27.4858\beta_{\text{opt}} - 28.1761. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A10})$$

Fig. 41.— A series of dust curves created by interpolating between the derived k_{base} parameterizations of the dust curves included in this study along with a smoothly varying contribution from k_{bump} .

As Fitzpatrick & Massa (2007), we opt to fit the NIR portion of the curve as a simple power law in x . Defining $x_{\text{NIR}} = 0.6800x$, we fit

$$k_{\text{NIR}}(\lambda) = I_1 (x_{\text{NIR}})^{I_2} + R_{\text{NIR}} \quad 6800 \text{ \AA} \leq \lambda \text{ \AA}, \quad (\text{A11})$$

where $R_{\text{NIR}} = k_{\text{opt}}(x = 0.6800^{-1} \mu\text{m}^{-1} | \beta_{\text{UV}}, \beta_{\text{opt}}) - I_1$ ensures continuity between the optical and NIR portions (Figure 37). The coefficients are well (likely over-)fit by cubic functions in β_{NIR} , such that

$$\begin{aligned} I_1 &= +4.0138\beta_{\text{NIR}}^3 - 48.1623\beta_{\text{NIR}}^2 - 192.0379\beta_{\text{NIR}} - 252.3266, \\ I_2 &= -0.6252\beta_{\text{NIR}}^3 - 9.4120\beta_{\text{NIR}}^2 - 45.7444\beta_{\text{NIR}} - 70.7515. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A12})$$

The 2175 \AA bump is fit using the same formalism presented above such that

$$k_{\text{bump}}(\lambda|c_b) = c_b D(x, x_0 = 4.952, \gamma = 0.922), \quad (\text{A13})$$

where the values of x_0 and γ are the mean values reported in Fitzpatrick & Massa (2007) and D is again the Drude function. The quality of the fits do not noticeably improve when the two parameters are left free, so we opt to fix them to decrease the number of free parameters in the fit (see Figure 38).

Taken together, we can write the entire reddening law parameterization as

$$k(\lambda) = k_{\text{base}}(\lambda|\beta_{\text{UV}}, \beta_{\text{opt}}, \beta_{\text{NIR}}, c_{\text{FUV}}) + k_{\text{bump}}(\lambda|c_b), \quad (\text{A14})$$

where

$$k_{\text{base}}(\lambda) = \begin{cases} k_{\text{FUV}}(\lambda|c_{\text{FUV}}) + k_{\text{UV}}(\lambda|\beta_{\text{UV}}), & \lambda < 2850 \text{ \AA}, \\ k_{\text{opt}}(\lambda|\beta_{\text{UV}}, \beta_{\text{opt}}), & 2850 \text{ \AA} \leq \lambda < 6800 \text{ \AA}, \\ k_{\text{NIR}}(\lambda|\beta_{\text{UV}}, \beta_{\text{opt}}, \beta_{\text{IR}}), & 6800 \text{ \AA} < \lambda. \end{cases} \quad (\text{A15})$$

Our final fits and errors are plotted in Figures 39 and 40, with a series of interpolated dust curves shown in Figure 41. Our final fitted parameters for each dust curve are listed in Table 3.

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Table 1. H -band cuts as a function of size

Deconvolved half-light radius (R_h)	H (mag)
0.112	24.583
0.126	24.598
0.141	24.603
0.158	24.597
0.178	24.582
0.2	24.557
0.224	24.484
0.251	24.398
0.282	24.307
0.316	24.213
0.355	24.116
0.398	24.016
0.447	23.913
0.501	23.808
0.562	23.7
0.631	23.59
0.708	23.479
0.794	23.366
0.891	23.251
1.0	23.135

Note. — H -band cuts as a function of the measured half-light radius R_h (measured in arcseconds) applied to our mock catalog (§ 3.1) to mimic the *WFIRST* sample. R_h was estimated by taking the R_h measured in Hubble Space Telescope (*HST*) Advanced Camera for Surveys (ACS) images and subtracting the point spread function (PSF) size in quadrature, while H was estimated from fitted templates.

Table 2. Derived equivalent widths for the Brown et al. (2014) templates

ID	log FUV	H α +N[II]	H β	H γ	O[II]	O[III] ₄₉₆₀	O[III] ₅₀₀₈
IC 0860	0.107	2.093	-2.809	-0.545	-0.985	1.22	3.395
NGC 4551	0.485	-1.06	-2.679	1.153	-1.369	1.693	3.185
NGC 0584	0.517	-2.305	-3.275	1.367	-0.991	1.194	-1.896
NGC 4125	0.524	1.312	-2.541	1.485	-1.169	0.785	0.321
NGC 5866	0.629	0.504	-2.226	1.535	-1.494	1.269	-0.225
IC 4051	0.653	0.839	-2.837	0.935	-1.361	2.335	2.303
NGC 4387	0.673	-0.903	-2.634	1.965	-1.406	1.275	3.032
NGC 3190	0.69	0.743	-3.291	0.625	-0.903	1.306	1.838
NGC 3379	0.691	-0.252	-2.388	1.182	-1.354	1.224	-1.758
NGC 2388	0.697	30.736	-1.367	-1.924	0.187	1.713	8.677
NGC 4458	0.708	-1.554	-3.004	0.244	-0.42	1.193	-0.606
NGC 0474	0.715	-0.654	-2.643	0.723	-0.918	1.425	-2.591
NGC 4168	0.725	0.148	-2.317	2.372	-1.047	1.039	-3.148
CGCG 049-057	0.751	13.56	-4.241	0.899	-1.143	4.896	9.134
NGC 4660	0.764	-0.829	-2.413	2.705	-1.394	0.985	2.587
NGC 4594	0.791	0.509	-1.691	3.09	-0.346	1.879	8.15
Mrk 1490	0.803	44.245	-1.905	-1.965	-0.145	1.057	4.119
NGC 4473	0.809	2.361	2.406	0.274	1.829	-0.869	-3.174
NGC 4621	0.809	-0.456	-2.681	1.311	-1.873	1.501	3.142
NGC 7585	0.829	0.289	-3.233	1.611	-1.082	1.705	0.036
UGC 12150	0.838	21.282	-2.907	-2.154	-0.022	1.54	10.977
NGC 4365	0.869	-0.88	-3.128	3.457	-0.92	1.14	0.815
NGC 0750	0.876	-0.002	-2.313	2.388	-1.319	1.104	-2.772
NGC 4926	0.902	-1.007	-2.994	2.719	-0.725	0.859	-4.609
NGC 4550	0.948	0.681	-2.788	0.249	0.244	1.678	2.25
NGC 4889	0.959	-0.208	-1.967	2.089	-1.356	0.762	-0.689
NGC 4552	0.98	-0.092	-2.167	2.788	-1.141	1.156	-1.498
NGC 5195	1.052	6.765	-2.818	-1.542	-0.414	2.007	7.324
NGC 4450	1.129	3.2	-2.456	2.121	-0.768	1.398	3.853
NGC 4486	1.186	2.691	-2.403	3.259	-1.149	1.54	-1.315
NGC 4860	1.187	-3.396	-2.544	1.558	-0.888	0.78	-0.608
IC 4553	1.234	16.539	-4.391	-3.407	0.62	1.153	8.988
Mrk 0331	1.303	56.039	0.701	-2.108	2.226	1.085	10.099
NGC 7331	1.31	7.446	-2.639	0.81	-0.681	0.359	1.515
IRAS 17208-0014	1.313	-0.212	-1.327	-4.747	0.317	1.456	20.681
NGC 0660	1.318	20.702	-3.524	-0.521	1.619	1.301	21.005
NGC 4725	1.338	4.78	-1.411	0.711	-1.317	0.674	1.759
NGC 5104	1.377	18.824	-2.555	-1.442	0.706	1.868	11.754
NGC 4579	1.391	7.225	-2.305	0.848	0.029	1.433	7.788
UGC 05101	1.409	17.427	-4.575	-3.703	2.756	4.319	12.498
UGC 09618 N	1.427	40.436	2.135	0.221	7.168	2.87	32.567

Table 2—Continued

ID	log FUV	H α +N[II]	H β	H γ	O[II]	O[III] ₄₉₆₀	O[III] ₅₀₀₈
NGC 3521	1.459	13.709	-2.11	-0.347	-0.196	1.481	3.727
NGC 4569	1.481	8.822	-3.372	-1.515	-0.003	1.223	5.463
NGC 4826	1.5	9.252	-1.557	0.865	-0.922	1.571	3.146
CGCG 453-062	1.543	52.113	1.934	-1.196	1.835	1.021	19.234
NGC 7771	1.606	22.34	-1.452	-0.786	-0.129	1.346	10.524
NGC 5033	1.628	17.818	-1.072	0.323	0.343	1.671	5.932
NGC 0520	1.658	6.313	-3.395	-3.124	-0.495	0.829	5.008
NGC 6240	1.68	79.629	1.566	-1.246	6.411	2.13	48.512
IC 5298	1.699	36.544	-0.161	-0.525	3.411	2.605	11.456
NGC 5953	1.707	50.435	1.817	-0.583	4.405	3.181	10.896
Arp 118	1.741	25.38	0.126	1.11	2.583	2.095	9.063
NGC 4676 A	1.752	14.152	-2.084	-2.041	1.402	1.526	4.635
UGC 08696	1.765	70.213	3.048	-1.108	34.776	12.112	45.0
NGC 4138	1.766	10.713	-1.264	0.441	0.902	1.584	11.997
NGC 2798	1.768	49.919	2.371	0.884	2.114	1.663	15.965
NGC 5055	1.784	12.001	-1.078	-3.394	-0.356	1.28	-0.372
NGC 3627	1.786	10.848	-2.704	-1.92	-0.213	1.389	4.621
NGC 3351	1.786	13.65	-0.605	1.313	-0.387	1.45	2.904
UGC 04881	1.803	16.84	-2.047	-2.584	0.622	1.206	8.535
III Zw 035	1.808	29.747	-0.877	-2.309	6.639	2.309	22.798
NGC 1144	1.83	42.133	2.163	1.162	4.071	2.713	13.528
UGC 09618	1.836	42.771	2.2	-0.387	6.339	2.255	23.991
NGC 7591	1.859	26.893	-0.57	-1.897	1.599	1.923	6.187
NGC 3079	1.944	32.715	0.525	-0.06	4.996	2.519	23.723
IC 0883	1.981	23.415	-3.82	-4.609	1.509	1.326	11.704
NGC 1068	2.003	65.914	2.164	0.376	29.549	7.144	12.32
NGC 4536	2.012	31.491	0.9	0.826	0.224	1.318	15.582
NGC 3265	2.036	35.734	1.603	0.792	1.498	2.147	16.861
NGC 3198	2.057	17.223	-0.859	-0.399	1.951	1.807	13.162
NGC 5653	2.068	58.944	3.374	-0.537	0.984	0.938	11.779
NGC 2623	2.079	9.589	-4.921	-4.404	-0.126	1.142	7.916
NGC 5258	2.107	32.256	0.149	-1.005	-0.583	2.582	1.089
NGC 4088	2.115	33.83	1.631	-1.534	2.359	1.336	13.105
NGC 0695	2.133	97.139	6.507	-0.649	5.296	2.956	23.144
NGC 5256	2.138	110.947	12.058	4.841	60.713	20.182	85.526
NGC 4254	2.157	39.605	1.402	-1.309	-0.189	1.573	5.274
NGC 5194	2.217	26.874	-0.614	-1.637	-0.333	1.263	0.721
NGC 5713	2.225	47.146	1.592	-1.745	1.105	1.708	17.021
NGC 1614	2.237	104.227	4.821	-1.102	6.261	2.538	17.564
NGC 4321	2.252	23.713	-0.461	-0.685	-0.22	1.7	5.446
UGC 08335 NW	2.261	32.343	-1.747	-0.257	6.528	1.71	18.187

Table 2—Continued

ID	log FUV	H α +N[II]	H β	H γ	O[II]	O[III] ₄₉₆₀	O[III] ₅₀₀₈
UGC 09618 S	2.293	49.65	2.635	-0.873	5.875	1.522	19.294
NGC 3938	2.311	18.116	0.812	-5.755	-3.309	4.478	-6.176
NGC 0855	2.318	24.483	1.49	0.489	9.411	3.923	35.78
NGC 4194	2.33	113.093	7.625	0.224	11.079	4.465	26.901
NGC 0628	2.333	6.353	-2.941	-1.163	-1.667	0.672	-1.063
UGC 08335 SE	2.35	32.294	-1.747	-0.257	6.528	1.71	18.187
IC 0691	2.39	133.409	21.446	7.524	48.353	16.898	95.585
NGC 7674	2.403	64.005	4.323	1.334	32.929	4.971	16.675
IRAS 08572+3915	2.423	-4.044	-1.336	-5.32	4.374	3.442	19.989
NGC 1275	2.431	52.819	2.496	0.632	11.547	0.866	40.914
NGC 4631	2.438	42.17	2.692	-1.617	10.731	4.283	30.24
CGCG 436-030	2.452	79.679	4.41	-1.041	6.004	2.232	32.848
NGC 4385	2.512	56.745	5.835	-0.602	3.351	2.771	24.507
NGC 3690	2.529	172.191	18.153	6.217	24.43	8.209	53.27
NGC 4625	2.552	30.304	0.299	-1.563	0.24	1.276	13.633
NGC 6090	2.564	174.871	16.692	3.879	13.042	4.88	32.205
NGC 7592	2.576	82.765	7.225	1.585	11.748	3.459	32.072
NGC 7679	2.599	96.514	6.597	-0.721	15.22	4.445	27.065
NGC 5257	2.615	84.235	6.921	1.296	6.796	3.735	24.628
NGC 0337	2.649	56.846	4.958	-0.917	11.962	5.438	36.423
NGC 4559	2.66	40.925	3.644	0.484	5.62	3.241	28.897
NGC 3049	2.682	65.395	6.997	2.529	2.955	2.176	21.121
Arp 256 S	2.706	144.653	14.351	2.689	16.251	5.041	45.095
NGC 5992	2.722	69.875	3.065	-2.129	8.017	3.329	24.366
NGC 2537	2.775	44.597	5.093	1.031	14.247	5.294	39.62
NGC 2403	2.796	40.263	2.204	0.348	5.364	3.589	19.226
Arp 256 N	2.873	78.794	9.213	2.309	10.968	4.424	35.083
NGC 3870	2.902	50.72	4.045	-0.236	15.81	5.847	51.733
NGC 7714	2.926	166.966	20.989	6.949	39.409	14.626	50.784
Mrk 33	2.962	136.25	19.54	6.214	42.64	15.514	66.661
UGC 06665	3.001	191.848	29.257	10.648	88.398	28.317	93.363
II Zw 096	3.015	130.53	14.586	3.57	32.748	11.695	51.419
UGCA 208	3.032	34.082	18.01	5.174	58.413	19.799	75.589
NGC 7673	3.064	121.199	15.499	2.906	34.784	12.212	56.955
NGC 6052	3.065	153.152	18.896	3.937	41.892	14.156	66.227
NGC 3773	3.071	75.971	12.059	4.264	20.9	6.446	47.118
NGC 3310	3.106	144.269	17.445	3.693	44.222	14.069	56.036
NGC 4670	3.135	105.84	18.313	5.693	50.831	17.596	53.653
UGCA 410	3.25	234.161	46.254	14.24	251.659	84.87	80.332
Mrk 0475	3.371	335.229	78.665	25.074	413.894	127.431	90.324
Haro 06	3.402	196.297	36.071	10.266	114.95	42.17	95.727

Table 2—Continued

ID	log FUV	H α +N[II]	H β	H γ	O[II]	O[III] ₄₉₆₀	O[III] ₅₀₀₈
Mrk 1450	3.504	430.038	96.572	28.213	483.533	160.582	117.336
UM 461	3.509	364.163	70.45	19.215	390.496	130.945	0.955
Mrk 0930	3.555	410.372	69.668	22.229	308.53	96.711	113.184
UGC 06850	3.627	287.527	52.295	13.046	228.586	79.041	75.651
UGCA 219	3.827	148.074	24.499	5.611	100.754	30.881	40.005
UGCA 166	4.504	856.074	129.955	39.924	235.194	72.863	24.653

Note. — FUV fluxes were derived using the *GALEX* FUV filter after each template was normalized to 1.6 μ m. All EWs are listed in units of \AA .

Table 3. Best-fitted dust curve parameterizations

Paper	Type	c_{FUV}	β_{UV}	β_{opt}	β_{IR}	c_b
Allen (1976)	MW	+0.0926	−2.1522	−1.6040	−4.2344	2.3692
Seaton (1979)	MW	+0.2599	−1.5929	−1.1254	−4.5728	3.9600
Calzetti et al. (2000)	SB	+0.0346	−2.3580	−1.5196	−4.8771	0.1703
Scoville et al. (2014)*	SFG	−0.1121	−0.6991	−1.4082	−3.3444	0.1346
Fitzpatrick (1986)	LMC	+0.4998	−2.0978	−1.1768	−3.8439	2.5450
Prevot et al. (1984)	SMC	+0.5545	−5.0606	−1.5158	−3.5602	0.5545

Note. — A list of fitted model parameters for the dust curves included in this study (see Appendix A and Figures 34–41).

*: Represents an earlier version of the data scaled to Prevot et al. (1984) rather than Calzetti et al. (2000). As the shape of the dust curve depends significantly on the chosen scale factor, this process dramatically affects the fitted parameters relative to the results reported in Scoville et al. (2014).